

Aladura Christianity in Nigeria

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Entry tags: Christianity, Religious Group, Language, English, Aladura, Yoruba Language

Aladura Christianity emerged in Nigeria in the early 20th century as a response to the perceived inadequacies of the Mainline Christian denominations in addressing the spiritual and physical needs of the people. The movement sought a return to what its founders believed were the authentic, spiritual roots of Christianity. Also, the emergence of this brand of Christianity could be said to be in reaction to a community in turmoil caused by hunger, the Great Depression, smallpox, and influenza outbreaks, which were some of the effects of the First World War. The term "Aladura" is a Yoruba word that translates to "owners of prayer" or "people of prayer." Aladura Christianity has played a significant role in the religious landscape of Nigeria. Key figures in the early history of the Aladura movement in Nigeria include Joseph Babalola of the Christ Apostolic Church (CAC), Moses Orimolade Tunolase and Christiana Abiodun Emanuel, prominent leaders associated with the Cherubim and Seraphim (C&S), Josiah Ositelu of the Church of the Lord - Aladura (CLA) and Samuel Bilewu Joseph Oschoffa of the Celestial Church of Christ (CCC). Since its founding as prayer gatherings inside more established Nigerian churches, particularly the Church Missionary Society (CMS), the Aladura churches have attracted a sizable following. Early in the 20th century, the Aladura churches flourished, although along ethnic lines, especially among the Yoruba. Over the years, this brand of Christianity has enjoyed significant patronage from other tribes. Salvation, repentance, forgiveness, holiness, healing, deliverance, exorcism, spiritual baptism, spiritual gifts, and spiritual authority are the foundational elements of Aladura Christianity. Aladura churches emphasise the importance of fervent prayer and spiritual warfare against forces of evil, and to retain the presence and power of the Holy Spirit. Members often engage in intense prayer sessions, deliverance services, and fasting. This movement places strong emphasis on divine healing and miracles through the power of the Holy Spirit. Healing services and the belief in the laying on of hands for healing are common practices. Their services are known for their vibrant and charismatic worship style, including lively music, dancing, and spontaneous expressions of faith. The movement embraces the charismatic and Pentecostal aspects of Christianity. Many Aladura churches have a strong prophetic ministry, where leaders and members believe in receiving and delivering messages from God through prophetic utterances. They often incorporate elements of indigenous African spirituality and cultural practices. The group's syncretic practices are evident in the use of indigenous languages, cultural symbols, and rituals. Aladura churches are often involved in community development, social welfare, and philanthropic activities. They play a role in addressing social issues such as poverty, education, and healthcare in their communities. It must be noted that while Aladura Christianity has its roots in Nigeria, it has spread to other parts of the world. Churches affiliated with the Aladura movement can be found in various countries with Nigerian and African communities. This brand of Christianity has contributed significantly to the diversity of Christian expression in Nigeria and has influenced the broader Pentecostal and Charismatic movements within the country.

Date Range: 1918 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

Nigeria, West Africa. Most Nigerian Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

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- Source 2: Idowu, E. B. (1965). *Towards an indigenous church*. London: Oxford University Press.
- Source 3: Ayegboyin, D., & Ishola, S. A. (1997). *African Indigenous churches: An historical perspective*. Lagos, Nigeria: Greater Heights.

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Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Atansuyi, H. O. (N.d). *Gospel and culture from the perspective of African Instituted Churches*. Cyberjournal for Pentecostal-Charismatic Research. Accessed February 6, 2019. <http://www.pctii.org/cyberj/cyberj3/aic.html>
- Source 2 URL: Ojo, Matthews A. "The Dynamics of Indigenous Charismatic Missionary Enterprises in West Africa." <http://www.oocities.org/missionalia/ojo1.htm> Accessed 20th February, 2019.
- Source 3 URL: Omoyajowo, Joseph Akin, Rt Revd Prof. "Gospel and Culture from the Perspective of African Churches." Funded by Foreign Missions. Online source accessed on 29th May, 2017 from <http://www.pctii.org/wcc/akin96.html>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UctJqRFyIvdiGpEXFryZjkSg>
- Source 1 Description: Official YouTube page of the Christ Apostolic Church
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCbjgK6Xfi3jDJF8ApmkwGIA>
- Source 2 Description: Official YouTube page of the Celestial Church of Christ
- Source 3 URL: https://web.facebook.com/p/CS-Unification-Church-of-Nigeria-100080148932404/?_rdc=1&_rdr
- Source 3 Description: Official Facebook page of the Cherubim & Seraphim Unification Church of Nigeria

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Aladura Christianity, emphasising healing and prophecy, sometimes attracts people from other faiths seeking spiritual solutions. This can lead to conversations and the sharing of practices. Also, members of Aladura churches live and work alongside people of other faiths. This social interaction fosters a natural exchange of ideas and customs. Moreso, Aladura Christianity stems from the Yoruba tradition, which has co-existed with Islam and even the Indigenous religions for centuries. There's a cross-pollination of concepts and rituals. In the same vein, we can say that in Nigeria, Aladura churches are a prominent religious force. They interact with other religious groups on national issues and social movements.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: Since there is no option for both yes and no, I will go for no, but in the actual sense of it, the cultural contact is complex. It can be competitive, with attempts to win converts or defend doctrines. But it also creates opportunities for collaboration and the enrichment of religious traditions through exchange. On the competitive aspect, we can say that some Aladura churches, like any religious group, see interaction as an opportunity to attract followers from other faiths. This creates a sense of competition for adherents. Also, differences in beliefs and practices between Aladura churches and other religions might lead to theological debates. For instance, the emphasis on healing and prophecy in Aladura churches might be contested by more conservative Christian denominations. However, on the collaborative aspect, despite the potential competition, Aladura churches also collaborate with others on social issues like poverty or education. This fosters a sense of common ground and mutual respect. Also, interaction often leads to the sharing of religious practices. For example, Aladura churches incorporate elements of indigenous healing from other African religions.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact between Aladura Christianity and other religious groups is seen as both accommodating and pluralistic, but with some limitations. In terms of accommodating aspects, Aladura Christianity, compared to more established Christian denominations, is often more open to incorporating elements of indigenous African religions like healing practices or veneration of ancestors. This shows a willingness to accommodate existing beliefs. Despite theological differences, Aladura Christianity might find common ground with other religions on shared values like morality, social justice, or family. This creates space for peaceful coexistence. On the pluralistic limitations, we can say that while Aladura Christianity is more open than some Christian denominations, there can still be a push to convert others. This can be seen as a limitation to true pluralism, which respects the right of individuals to hold different beliefs. Also, social and political tensions have, at one point in time or another, spilled over into religious spheres, creating distrust or friction between Aladura Christianity and other groups. In all, cultural contact has elements of accommodation and pluralism. Aladura Christianity shows a degree of openness to other traditions, but there are still limitations, particularly when it comes to fully embracing religious diversity.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The cultural contact between Aladura Christianity and other cultures is a complex interplay, with elements of competition, collaboration, accommodation, and tension. Different cultures promote specific values and worldviews. When these come into contact, there's bound to be some tension or attempt to influence each other. Also, culture does not exist in a vacuum; social and political issues can influence how they interact. For instance, competition for resources or political power can create conflict.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: While there have not been widespread reports of violent conflict specifically between Aladura Christianity and other cultural contacts, cultural cum religious tensions do exist in Nigeria, and some Aladura churches are indirectly affected. Nevertheless, every culture is permitted, and none is discriminated against.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: There is no violent conflict whatsoever with groups outside the sample region. They live in peace and harmony with both members and non-members alike. Nevertheless, some Aladura churches have been indirectly affected by the different cultural and religious tensions that are very prominent in the country.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: While Aladura churches share common beliefs and practices, there is no centralised authority or uniform process for assigning religious affiliation within the movement. Instead, membership in Aladura churches typically involves a personal decision to join a specific congregation or denomination within the broader Aladura movement. This decision are influenced by factors such as family background, personal spiritual experiences, or theological alignment with a particular church's teachings. Aladura churches are often organised into denominations, such as the Cherubim and Seraphim Society, the Church of the Lord (Aladura), Christ Apostolic Church, Celestial Church of Christ, and some other denominations. Each denomination has its own structure for admitting new members, which often involves baptism, confirmation, or other rituals. However, there is no standardised or universal process for assigning religious affiliation within Aladura Christianity. Membership is typically based on individual choice and participation in the worship and activities of a particular congregation or denomination.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Aladura Christianity, like many religious movements, engages in evangelism and outreach activities to spread their beliefs and attract new members. These activities include preaching, prayer meetings, healing services, and community outreach programmes. However, the extent to which individual Aladura churches engage in proselytisation and recruitment varies depending on factors such as cultural context, leadership style, and theological emphasis. Some Aladura churches actively seek to convert individuals from other religious backgrounds or non-religious affiliations through evangelistic campaigns or personal evangelism efforts. Others may focus more on nurturing and retaining existing members within their own communities.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: In many religious traditions, including Christianity, the mandate for proselytising or evangelism, as the case may be, varies based on theological interpretations and denominational beliefs. Within Aladura Christianity, the emphasis on proselytising slightly differs among individual churches and denominations. For some religious professionals within Aladura Christianity, such as pastors, evangelism and spreading the faith are considered central to their calling and responsibilities. Some see it as part of fulfilling the Great Commission, as outlined in the Bible, where Jesus instructs his disciples to "go and make disciples of all nations" (Matthew 28:19). As such, they actively engage in evangelistic activities and encourage others to do the same. However, not all religious professionals within Aladura Christianity view proselytising as a mandated duty. Some prioritise pastoral care, spiritual guidance, and nurturing the existing faith community over actively seeking new converts. Additionally, individual interpretations of religious texts and theological teachings shape individual religious professional's approaches to evangelism. Ultimately, whether proselytising is mandated for religious professionals within Aladura Christianity or not varies based on factors such as denominational teachings, personal beliefs, and cultural contexts within the specific congregation or denomination.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the mandate for proselytising or evangelism is often considered an important aspect of the faith, but not mandated for all adherents in the same way it is for religious professionals. The emphasis on evangelism and spreading the faith varies among individual adherents within Aladura Christianity. Some adherents feel a strong personal conviction to share their beliefs with others and actively engage in evangelistic efforts as part of their spiritual practice. Such see evangelism as a natural outgrowth of their faith and a way to fulfil the Great Commission of Jesus to "go and make disciples of all nations" (Matthew 28:19). However, not all adherents feel equally compelled to proselytise. Factors such as cultural background, personal temperament, and individual interpretations of religious teachings influence an adherent's approach to evangelism. Some adherents prioritise living out their faith through acts of service, charity, and personal example over actively seeking to convert others.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: The mandate for missionary work among religious professionals within Aladura Christianity varies depending on the specific denomination, theological teachings, and individual interpretations of scripture. In many Christian traditions, including Aladura Christianity, there is a strong emphasis on spreading the gospel and fulfilling the Great Commission of Jesus Christ which includes making disciples of all nations (Matthew 28:19-20). As such, many religious professionals, such as pastors, prophets/prophetesses, and evangelists within Aladura Christianity, feel a strong calling to engage in missionary work as part of their ministry. For some religious professionals within Aladura Christianity, missionary work is considered a central aspect of their vocation and ministry responsibilities. They actively participate in missionary activities, such as evangelism, church planting, and community development, both locally and internationally. However, the extent to which missionary work is mandated for all religious professionals within Aladura Christianity varies due to factors such as denominational teachings, individual convictions and practical considerations. While some

religious professionals prioritise missionary work as a primary focus of their ministry, others focus more on pastoral care, teaching, or other aspects of ministry without necessarily engaging in extensive missionary activities.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Within Aladura Christianity, the mandate for missionary work, like evangelism, is not universally mandated for all adherents in the same explicit manner it is for religious professionals or leaders. However, the importance of missionary work is often emphasised within the broader context of spreading the faith and fulfilling the Great Commission of Jesus Christ. While missionary work is encouraged and considered a vital aspect of the faith, not all adherents feel personally called or compelled to engage in missionary activities. Factors such as individual abilities, circumstances, and personal convictions influence an adherent's decision to participate in missionary work. Some adherents actively engage in missionary activities, whether locally or internationally, as an expression of their faith and commitment to sharing the gospel with others. This involves activities such as evangelism, community development, education, healthcare, and humanitarian aid. However, other adherents focus more on living out their faith through personal piety, worship, and involvement in their local faith community without necessarily engaging in formal missionary work.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: There is nothing like coercion when it comes to proselytisation by the Aladura churches.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: This religious organisation does not have official political support whatsoever. However, within specific regions or countries where Aladura churches are present, individual churches or denominations have varying degrees of interaction with political authorities. In some cases, certain branches of Aladura Christianity have connections or affiliations with political figures or parties while others maintain a more independent or apolitical stance.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in many religious traditions, there is a concept of apostasy, which refers to the abandonment or renunciation of one's faith. Apostasy is generally viewed negatively within Aladura Christianity, as it is seen as a departure from the teachings and beliefs of the faith.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: In a country that upholds the rule of law and values human life with freedom of association, such practice is not permitted. The Aladura churches do not prosecute or punish apostates.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 7000000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 3.1

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, within the Aladura religious group, there are recognised leaders who play significant roles in guiding the spiritual life of the community and overseeing the administration of religious practices. These leaders hold titles such as pastors, bishops, prophets, or overseers, depending on the specific denomination or branch of Aladura Christianity. These leaders are ordained clergy who have undergone training and received recognition from their respective denominations or religious communities. They are responsible for providing spiritual guidance, leading worship services, administering sacraments, and overseeing the pastoral care of their congregations. In addition to ordained clergy, there are recognised prophets or spiritual elders who are believed to have special gifts of prophecy, spiritual insight, or healing. These individuals hold respected positions within the community and play significant roles in guiding the religious beliefs and practices of the group.

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Within the Aladura religious group, there is often a well-defined hierarchical structure among its leaders, particularly within organised denominations or churches. This hierarchical framework serves to establish lines of authority, ensure accountability, and facilitate the administration of spiritual affairs within the community. At the top of the hierarchy, there is a founding figure or successor who holds significant authority within the denomination. This individual, often recognised as the general overseer (Olori) or presiding bishop, as the case may be, provides overarching leadership and guidance to the denomination as a whole. They oversee multiple churches or congregations and play a central role in setting the spiritual direction and policies of the denomination. Some denominations have leaders-in-council that will include the elders of the denomination. Beneath the general overseer, bishops, or leader-in-charge who hold positions of authority within specific regions, branches, or dioceses. These senior clergy are responsible for overseeing the spiritual and administrative affairs of their respective jurisdictions, which may encompass multiple churches or congregations. They provide guidance and support to pastors, prophets/prophetesses, visioners and congregations under their care, ensuring the implementation of denominational doctrines and practices. At the local level, pastors or ministers serve as the spiritual leaders of individual congregations or churches. They are responsible for preaching, teaching, providing pastoral care, and

administering sacraments to their congregants. These people play a central role in nurturing the spiritual growth and well-being of their congregations, while also representing the denomination within their local communities. Supporting the ordained clergy are elders and deacons, who serve in auxiliary roles within congregations. These individuals assist pastors in various aspects of ministry and provide leadership within the local church community. Their roles include assisting with worship services, leading small groups, and providing support to congregants in need. In addition to ordained clergy, there are recognised prophets or spiritual leaders who hold esteemed positions within the community. These individuals are believed to possess special gifts of prophecy, spiritual insight, or healing and may play significant roles in guiding the religious beliefs and practices of the denomination.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: Within individual local communities or congregations within Aladura Christianity, leadership is often vested in a single individual who serves as the pastor or minister of the church. This prophet/prophetess, pastor or minister is responsible for providing spiritual guidance, leading worship services, teaching, and offering pastoral care to the members of the congregation. While the pastor or minister holds significant authority within the local community, they are typically accountable to a higher level of leadership within their denomination or church organisation. This could include oversight from bishops, regional leaders, and leaders-in-council, or denominational authorities who ensure adherence to doctrinal standards, provide support and guidance to pastors, and facilitate coordination among churches within the denomination. Therefore, while there may not be a single overarching leader for all Aladura churches in a given region, there is often a single leader at the local level who oversees the spiritual life and activities of a specific congregation or community.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: There are multiple religious communities within the broad Aladura Classification. Each of these groups is with its own leader or pastor overseeing the spiritual life and activities of the community. These leaders have authority within their respective congregations or communities and are responsible for providing spiritual guidance, leading worship services, and administering pastoral care to their members. While there may not be a formal hierarchy among these leaders in the sense of one leader overseeing all others, there is often a recognition of leadership roles and responsibilities within individual communities or congregations. Each leader operates within the context of their own religious community, with autonomy to make decisions and provide direction based on the needs and beliefs of their congregation. However, it is important to note that while there may not be a hierarchical structure among leaders at the local level, there may still be connections or affiliations with broader denominational structures or networks that provide support, accountability, and guidance to individual leaders and communities. Leaders may collaborate with one another on matters of mutual concern or interest, fostering a sense of unity and cooperation within the broader Aladura Christian movement.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, within Aladura Christianity, there are often regional leaders who oversee one or more local leaders, such as bishops or overseers. These regional leaders typically have authority over a specific geographic area or jurisdiction within a denomination or church organisation. Regional leaders, often referred to as bishops (like in the Church of the Lord (Aladura) or overseers, play significant roles in providing guidance, support, and oversight to pastors and congregations within their jurisdiction. They may have responsibilities such as appointing pastors to serve in local congregations, providing pastoral care and counselling to pastors and congregants, and ensuring adherence to denominational doctrine and practices. These regional leaders may also facilitate coordination and collaboration among local churches within their jurisdiction, promoting unity and cooperation within the broader religious community. They serve as intermediaries between the local congregations and higher levels of denominational leadership, helping to ensure effective communication and accountability within the denomination.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, within Aladura Christianity, there are often councils or groups of leaders at higher levels of authority that provide oversight and guidance to leaders at lower levels within a region or denomination. These councils or groups may vary in structure and composition depending on the specific denomination or organisational structure. At the regional level, there may be councils of bishops or overseers who collectively provide leadership and oversight to pastors and congregations within a specific geographic area. These councils may meet regularly to discuss matters of doctrine, governance, and administration, and to provide support and guidance to pastors and congregations under their jurisdiction. Additionally, there may be national or denominational councils or assemblies composed of leaders from various regions or jurisdictions within the denomination. These higher-level councils may have the authority to make decisions on behalf of the denomination as a whole, set policies and guidelines, and provide direction for the broader religious community. While there may be councils or groups of leaders that provide oversight at higher levels within Aladura Christianity, it is important to note that the degree of centralised authority and decision-making can vary among different denominations and branches of the movement. Some may have more centralised structures with formalised councils or assemblies, while others may have more decentralised structures with greater autonomy granted to individual regions or congregations.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the hierarchy of religious leadership typically consists of multiple levels, though the specific structure can vary among different denominations

or branches of the movement. Below is a rough estimate of the potential levels in the hierarchy: Local Leaders: At the base of the hierarchy are local leaders, such as pastors or ministers, who oversee individual congregations or communities. Regional Leaders: Above local leaders, there may be regional leaders, such as bishops or overseers, who provide oversight to multiple congregations within a specific geographic area or jurisdiction. Denominational Leaders: At a higher level, there may be denominational leaders, such as general overseers, presiding bishops, or founders' successors, who provide leadership and direction to the denomination as a whole. National or International Leaders: Some denominations may have national or international leaders who oversee multiple regions or denominational branches within a country or across different countries. Councils or Assemblies: In addition to individual leaders, there may be councils, assemblies, or synods composed of leaders from various levels within the denomination. These bodies may make decisions on behalf of the denomination, set policies and guidelines, and provide overall direction for the religious community. These are general levels within the hierarchy of religious leadership in Aladura Christianity, but the actual structure may vary in complexity and formality depending on the denomination or organisational structure. Additionally, there may be variations within specific denominations based on cultural context, historical factors, and other considerations.

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, some leaders are believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities, particularly those who are recognised as prophets or spiritual elders. These individuals are often regarded as having special spiritual gifts, such as the ability to prophesy, heal, or receive divine revelation. Within the framework of Aladura Christianity, spiritual gifts are seen as manifestations of the Holy Spirit's presence and power, and they are believed to be bestowed upon individuals for the edification and benefit of the religious community. Leaders who are believed to possess such gifts may be revered and respected within their communities, and their guidance and counsel may be sought on matters of spiritual significance. It is important to note that beliefs about spiritual gifts and the role of leaders may vary among different denominations or branches of Aladura Christianity, and not all leaders may be believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities. Additionally, beliefs about spiritual gifts should be understood within the broader theological context of the movement, which emphasises the authority of the Bible and the power of prayer in conjunction with spiritual manifestations.

Reference: Peel, John. Aladura. Oxford University Press, 1968.

Reference: Ray, Benjamin C.. "Aladura Christianity: A Yoruba Religion" 23, no. 3 (August 1993). <https://doi.org/10.2307/1581109>.

Reference: Omoyajowo, J. Akinyele. Cherubim and Seraphim, the History of an African Independent Church. NOK Publishers International, 1982.

Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: The belief that powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives is not a characteristic belief within mainstream Aladura Christianity. Aladura Christianity, like other branches of Christianity, generally adheres to the belief in a single lifetime for each individual, with the opportunity for salvation and spiritual

growth within that lifetime. Within Aladura Christianity, spiritual powers or gifts are typically understood within the context of the Holy Spirit's work in the lives of believers, rather than being attributed to actions in past lives. These gifts are often seen as manifestations of the Holy Spirit's presence and are believed to be bestowed upon individuals for the benefit of the religious community. It is important to recognise that beliefs and practices can vary among different denominations and branches within Aladura Christianity, and there may be variations in beliefs about spiritual gifts. However, the belief in reincarnation and the acquisition of powers through past lives is not a characteristic belief within mainstream Aladura Christianity.

Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life is not a prominent or characteristic belief. Instead, spiritual gifts or powers within Aladura Christianity are typically understood within the context of the Holy Spirit's work in the lives of believers. According to Aladura Christian theology, spiritual gifts are manifestations of the Holy Spirit's presence and are bestowed upon individuals for the edification and benefit of the religious community. These gifts may include abilities such as prophecy, healing, speaking in tongues, and discernment of spirits, among others. The acquisition of spiritual gifts within Aladura Christianity is often believed to be a result of the individual's faith, prayer life, and relationship with God, rather than being directly tied to specific deeds or actions. Individuals are encouraged to cultivate their spiritual lives through prayer, study of scripture, participation in worship, and engagement in acts of service and ministry. While individuals may develop and exercise spiritual gifts through their actions and experiences in their current lives, the belief that powers are acquired solely through individual deeds is not a central tenet of Aladura Christianity. Instead, the emphasis is on the role of the Holy Spirit in empowering believers for service and ministry within the church and the broader community.

Powers are inherited:

– No

Notes: Within Aladura Christianity, the belief that spiritual powers are inherited is not a universally held doctrine. While Aladura Christianity, like many other Christian movements, emphasises the importance of spiritual gifts and the empowerment of believers by the Holy Spirit, the specific beliefs about the inheritance of spiritual powers can vary among different denominations and individual adherents. In some branches of Aladura Christianity, there may be a belief in the transmission of spiritual gifts or powers through familial lines, particularly within certain lineages or families with a history of spiritual leadership or prominence. This belief may be based on the idea of spiritual inheritance or lineage, where individuals inherit spiritual authority or gifts from their ancestors or lineage members who were recognised as spiritual leaders or prophets. However, it is essential to recognise that beliefs about the inheritance of spiritual powers are not universal within Aladura Christianity, and they may not be emphasised or accepted by all adherents or denominations. The emphasis on spiritual gifts and empowerment within Aladura Christianity is typically rooted in the belief in the work of the Holy Spirit in the lives of believers, rather than in the concept of inherited powers. As with any religious tradition, beliefs and practices within Aladura Christianity can vary widely, and interpretations of spiritual concepts may differ among

individuals and communities. Therefore, while some adherents may hold beliefs about the inheritance of spiritual powers, these beliefs may not be representative of the entire Aladura Christian movement.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity generally emphasises the Holy Spirit as the source of spiritual gifts and powers. They believe the Holy Spirit empowers individuals for healing, prophecy, and other miraculous abilities. Developing these powers is often seen as a result of prayer, faith, and living a righteous life according to Christian principles. There is not a concept of a singular supernatural being directly transmitting these powers culturally.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that spiritual powers are culturally transmitted from another human, such as a spiritual mentor or teacher, is not prominent or characteristic. Instead, the emphasis is typically on the role of the Holy Spirit in bestowing spiritual gifts and empowerment upon believers. While spiritual mentors or leaders may play important roles in guiding and nurturing the spiritual development of individuals within the Aladura Christian community, the transmission of spiritual powers is generally understood to be a divine act facilitated by the Holy Spirit, rather than a result of human influence or cultural transmission. Aladura Christianity places a strong emphasis on the authority of scripture, the power of prayer, and the work of the Holy Spirit in the lives of believers. Spiritual gifts, such as prophecy, healing, and speaking in tongues, are believed to be manifestations of the Holy Spirit's presence and are bestowed upon individuals according to God's will, rather than being passed down through human lineage or mentorship. While spiritual mentors or teachers may serve as vessels through which individuals are inspired, mentored, and nurtured in their faith, the belief in the transmission of spiritual powers directly from another human is not a central tenet of Aladura Christianity. Instead, the focus is on the relationship between the individual believer and God, with spiritual empowerment ultimately coming from the Holy Spirit.

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, there is a belief that certain spiritual gifts and powers may be associated with the leadership office that individuals assume within the religious community. This belief is rooted in the understanding that God may empower leaders with specific gifts and abilities to fulfil their roles effectively and to serve the needs of the community. Leaders within Aladura Christianity, such as pastors, bishops, or overseers, are often seen as having been called by God and appointed to their positions of authority within the church. As such, they may be believed to possess spiritual gifts and powers that are relevant to their leadership responsibilities. For example, pastors may be believed to have the gift of preaching or teaching, enabling them to effectively communicate the message of the gospel to their congregations. Bishops or overseers may be believed to have the gift of discernment or wisdom,

enabling them to provide guidance and oversight to multiple congregations or regions within the denomination. Additionally, certain leadership offices within Aladura Christianity may be associated with specific spiritual gifts or manifestations of the Holy Spirit. For example, prophets or spiritual elders may be recognised for their ability to prophesy or discern spiritual matters, while evangelists may be gifted with sharing the gospel and leading others to faith.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the selection of religious leaders is a multifaceted process that varies among different denominations of the movement. One common belief is that leaders are chosen by God through a process of divine call or inspiration. This divine call is typically discerned through prayer, spiritual guidance, and confirmation from other members of the religious community. Individuals who feel called to leadership roles may undergo a period of discernment and preparation before accepting their role within the church. Another method of selecting religious leaders is through appointment by higher authorities within the church hierarchy. In some denominations, leaders are appointed or ordained by bishops, overseers, or other senior clergy. These appointments are often based on criteria such as the individual's spiritual maturity, theological training, and suitability for the role. The authority to appoint leaders may rest with a single individual or with a council of elders or bishops within the denomination. In congregational or democratic denominations, religious leaders may be chosen through a process of election or consensus among the members of the congregation or church community. Candidates for leadership positions may be nominated and voted upon by the congregation, with the final decision being made through a democratic process. This ensures that leaders are selected with the consent and support of the congregation. Additionally, in some denominations or lineages within Aladura Christianity, leadership positions may be passed down through familial lines or established succession plans. This may involve the designation of a successor by the current leader or by a council of elders within the denomination. Succession planning ensures continuity of leadership and may involve mentoring and training the successor to assume their role effectively.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

Notes: In some denominations within Aladura Christianity leaders exercise influence in choosing their successor. For example, Moses Orimolade chose his successor for his own brand of Cherubim and Seraphim Church (Eternal Sacred Order of Cherubim and Seraphim Church). This succession process can vary depending on the specific traditions and practices of the denomination or religious community as the decision-making process for selecting a successor involves various factors, including the leader's assessment of the individual's spiritual maturity, leadership abilities, and alignment with the vision and values of the religious community. The leader may also seek guidance from trusted advisors or spiritual mentors in making this decision. Additionally, the leader may play a role in mentoring and preparing their chosen successor. This may involve providing guidance, training, and support to ensure a smooth transition of leadership within the religious community. However, it is important to note that not all denominations of Aladura Christianity follow this practice. In congregational or democratic denominations, for example, leaders may be selected through a process of election or consensus among the members of the congregation, rather than being chosen by the outgoing leader.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

Notes: In certain instances within Aladura Christianity, particularly in denominations or branches where leadership decisions are made collectively, a leader's retinue or ministers may play a significant role in the selection of a new leader. This process can reflect a democratic or consensus-based approach to leadership succession within the religious community. In this scenario, the retinue or ministers, who are trusted advisors and assistants to the leader, may collaborate to identify potential candidates for the leadership position. They may consider various factors, such as spiritual maturity, leadership abilities, and alignment with the vision and values of the religious community when evaluating candidates. Once potential candidates have been identified, the retinue or ministers may engage in discussions, consultations, and prayerful discernment to reach a consensus on the best candidate to succeed the outgoing leader. This process may involve input from other members of the congregation or religious community to ensure broad-based support for the decision. Ultimately, the retinue or ministers may present their recommendation or nomination for the new leader to the congregation or relevant governing body for approval. The decision-making process may vary depending on the specific governance structures and traditions of the denomination or religious community.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, it is uncommon for a political leader to directly choose a new religious leader. Aladura Christianity typically operates independently of political influence, with leadership decisions made within the religious community itself. The selection of a new religious leader in Aladura Christianity is usually guided by spiritual principles, theological considerations, and established religious practices within the denomination or branch. This process often involves consultation, prayer, and discernment among religious leaders, elders, and members of the congregation. While political leaders may have relationships with religious leaders and may offer support or recognition to religious institutions, the appointment or selection of a new religious leader is generally regarded as an internal matter within the religious community. Political leaders typically do not have authority or jurisdiction over religious leadership appointments in Aladura Christianity.

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

Notes: In certain instances within Aladura Christianity, particularly in congregational or democratic denominations, other members of the leader's congregation may indeed play a significant role in choosing a new leader. This process reflects a participatory approach to leadership succession, where decisions are made collectively with input from the congregation members. When a leadership vacancy occurs, members of the congregation may be invited to participate in the selection process. This could involve nominations of potential candidates from within the congregation or nominations put

forward by a leadership council or committee. Members of the congregation may have the opportunity to provide feedback on potential candidates and to express their preferences through discussions, meetings, or voting processes. However, this is often in rare occasions, as leadership enthronement is often a very dicey one when it comes to Aladura Christianity.

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: All members of the religious group in the sample region do not participate in choosing the leader. However, while full congregational participation might not be the norm, there could be elements of consultation with church members or key leaders before finalising the selection.

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, leaders are generally considered fallible, meaning they are subject to making mistakes or errors in judgment. While leaders are respected and often regarded as spiritual authorities within the religious community, they are not considered infallible or without fault. Aladura Christianity, like other Christian traditions, upholds the belief in the fallen nature of humanity, stemming from the doctrine of original sin. This doctrine teaches that all human beings, including religious leaders, are inherently flawed and prone to sin. As such, leaders in Aladura Christianity are understood to be imperfect and capable of making mistakes, just like any other member of the congregation. However, despite their fallibility, leaders in Aladura Christianity are still expected to demonstrate integrity, humility, and accountability in their leadership roles. They are called to uphold the teachings of scripture, to lead by example, and to serve the needs of the congregation with sincerity and compassion.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers can indeed occur, reflecting the acknowledgement that leaders, like all individuals, are subject to making mistakes or errors in judgment. While leaders in Aladura Christianity are generally respected and regarded as spiritual authorities within their religious communities, they are not considered infallible. Charges of fallibility made by a leader's followers may arise for various reasons, such as concerns about moral integrity, ethical conduct, or leadership decisions perceived as detrimental to the well-being of the congregation. Followers may raise these charges through internal channels within the religious community, such as meetings, discussions, or complaints to higher authorities within the denomination.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, charges of fallibility can be made by other leaders within the Aladura Christian community. In Aladura Christianity, as in many religious traditions, there is a recognition that leaders, while respected and entrusted with authority, are still fallible human beings subject to making mistakes or errors in judgment. When charges of fallibility arise from other leaders within the religious group, they may stem from concerns about moral integrity, ethical conduct, or leadership decisions perceived as harmful or inappropriate. These charges may be brought forward through established channels of accountability and oversight within the denomination or religious community.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, charges of fallibility made by a political ruler would be a rare occurrence and would likely be viewed with scepticism or concern within the religious community. Aladura Christianity, like many other religious traditions, typically operates independently of political influence, and leadership decisions are primarily guided by spiritual principles, theological considerations, and the needs of the religious community rather than political considerations. If charges of fallibility were to be made by a political ruler against a religious leader in Aladura Christianity, it could potentially raise questions about the motives behind the accusations and the appropriate boundaries between religious and political authority. Religious leaders in Aladura Christianity are generally expected to operate with integrity, humility, and accountability within the context of their religious responsibilities, rather than being subject to external interference or influence from political authorities. However, it is important to note that interactions between religious and political leaders can vary depending on the specific cultural and historical context. In some cases, political rulers may seek to exert influence over religious institutions for various reasons, such as to gain support or legitimacy. In such instances, charges of fallibility made by a political ruler could potentially be perceived as attempts to undermine or discredit the religious leadership for political purposes.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the extent to which close followers or disciples of a religious leader are required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters can vary depending on the specific beliefs, practices, and dynamics within the religious community. While respect for religious leaders and their teachings is typically emphasised within Aladura Christianity, followers are generally encouraged to exercise discernment, critical thinking, and personal prayer in evaluating the guidance and teachings of their leaders. Obedience to religious leaders is often understood within the context of humility, trust, and submission to spiritual authority, rather than blind adherence to every pronouncement or decree.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Yes, Aladura Christianity, like other Christian denominations, recognises the Bible as its primary scripture. The Bible is considered the inspired word of God and serves as the authoritative source of doctrine, belief, and practice within Aladura Christianity. Within Aladura Christianity, the Bible is studied, revered, and interpreted in various ways, depending on the denomination, theological tradition, and cultural context. It serves as the foundation for worship, preaching, teaching, and spiritual formation within the Aladura Christian community, guiding believers in matters of faith, ethics, and conduct.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Since this is a Christian religious group, they uphold the use of the Christian Holy Scripture known as the Bible. The Bible is typically composed of two main sections: the Old Testament and the New Testament. The Old Testament contains writings that are sacred to both Judaism and Christianity, including the Torah (the first five books of the Hebrew Bible), historical narratives, wisdom literature, and prophetic writings. The New Testament contains writings that focus on the life, teachings, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ, as well as the early Christian church.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: The scripture of the Aladura Christianity is not oral. It is written.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in other Christian traditions, there isn't a specific story associated with the origin of scripture exclusive to this denomination. Instead, the origin of scripture is understood within the broader Christian context, which acknowledges the Bible as the inspired word of God. The belief in the divine inspiration of scripture is foundational to Aladura Christianity, and it is generally understood that the various books of the Bible were written by human authors under the guidance and inspiration of the Holy Spirit. The process of how these writings came to be recognised as scripture and included in the biblical canon is a topic of historical and theological study within Christianity as a whole.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Just like the broader Christian context, Aladura Christianity acknowledges the Bible as the inspired word of God. They believe the Scripture has divine inspiration. It is generally understood that the various books of the Bible were written by human authors under the guidance and inspiration of the Holy Spirit. The process of how these writings came to be recognised as scripture and included in the biblical canon is a topic of historical and theological study within Christianity as a whole.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Majorly, the other supernatural being is the Holy Spirit. It is generally understood that the various books of the Bible were written by human authors under the guidance and inspiration of the Holy Spirit. The process of how these writings came to be recognised as scripture and included in the biblical canon is a topic of historical and theological study within Christianity as a whole.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in other Christian traditions, the belief is that scripture originated from divine inspiration rather than from semi-divine human beings. The Bible considered the authoritative scripture within Aladura Christianity, is believed to be the inspired word of God, communicated through human authors under the guidance and inspiration of the Holy Spirit. The doctrine of divine inspiration teaches that while the Bible was written by human authors, it is ultimately God's revelation to humanity. The Holy Spirit inspired and guided the authors in their writing, ensuring that the message conveyed in the scriptures is divinely inspired and without error in matters of faith and practice. This understanding of scripture aligns with traditional Christian theology, which holds that the Bible is the inspired and authoritative word of God, capable of guiding believers in matters of faith, doctrine, and moral conduct. While human authors played a role in writing the biblical texts, their writings are considered to be divinely inspired and carry the authority of God himself.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: No, Aladura Christianity, like other Christian denominations, does not believe that scripture originated solely from non-divine human beings. Instead, it holds to the doctrine of divine inspiration, which teaches that the Bible is the inspired word of God communicated through human authors under the guidance of the Holy Spirit. According to this belief, while human beings physically wrote the books of the Bible, they did so under the influence of divine inspiration. The Holy Spirit inspired and guided these human authors, ensuring that the message conveyed in the scriptures is divinely inspired and without error in matters of faith and practice. This understanding of scripture as originating from divine inspiration is foundational to Aladura Christianity and is consistent with traditional Christian theology. It emphasises the belief that the Bible carries the authority of God himself and is capable of guiding believers in matters

of faith, doctrine, and moral conduct.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in other Christian denominations, the scriptures are generally regarded as unalterable in terms of their divine authority and content. The Bible, considered the authoritative scripture within Aladura Christianity, is believed to be the inspired word of God, and its teachings are seen as timeless and unchanging. The belief in the unalterability of scripture stems from the understanding that the Bible is divinely inspired and carries the authority of God himself. While human beings may interpret and apply the teachings of scripture in various ways, the content of the Bible itself is considered to be fixed and immutable. Attempts to alter or change the content of scripture would be viewed as tampering with the word of God and would likely be met with strong opposition within Aladura Christianity. The integrity and reliability of the Bible as the inspired word of God are foundational to the faith, and any changes to its content would undermine its authority and authenticity.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, formal institutions for interpreting the scriptures exist, although the extent and nature of these institutions vary among different denominations, congregations, and cultural contexts within the religious community. Some Aladura Christian denominations have formal institutions or bodies tasked with the interpretation of scripture and the development of theological doctrine. These institutions include seminaries, theological schools, or academies where clergy and lay leaders receive training in biblical interpretation, theology, and pastoral ministry. These institutions may be authorised by the denominational leadership or recognised as official educational institutions within the religious community. Additionally, some denominations or congregations within Aladura Christianity have theological councils, doctrinal committees, or councils of elders responsible for providing guidance and oversight in matters of biblical interpretation and theological doctrine. These bodies may be composed of clergy, theologians, and other experts who are recognised for their knowledge and expertise in scripture and theology. However, it is important to note that the interpretation of scripture is not solely the purview of formal institutions within Aladura Christianity. The reading and interpretation of the Bible are also encouraged among individual believers, who may engage in personal study, prayer, and reflection to discern the meaning and application of scripture in their lives. Furthermore, while formal institutions may provide guidance and expertise in biblical interpretation, the ultimate authority for interpreting scripture is typically considered to rest with the entire faith community rather than with any single individual or institution. The collective discernment of the community, guided by the Holy Spirit, is valued as an important aspect of interpreting scripture within Aladura Christianity.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: The interpretation of scripture is not solely the purview of formal institutions within Aladura Christianity. The reading and interpretation of the Bible are also encouraged among individual believers, who may engage in personal study, prayer, and

reflection to discern the meaning and application of scripture in their lives. Furthermore, while formal institutions may provide guidance and expertise in biblical interpretation, the ultimate authority for interpreting scripture is typically considered to rest with the entire faith community rather than with any single individual or institution. The collective discernment of the community, guided by the Holy Spirit, is valued as an important aspect of interpreting scripture within Aladura Christianity.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

Notes: The interpretation of scripture is not solely within the purview of formal institutions within Aladura Christianity. The reading and interpretation of the Bible are also encouraged among individual believers who may engage in personal study, prayer, and reflection to discern the meaning and application of scripture in their lives. Furthermore, while formal institutions may provide guidance and expertise in biblical interpretation, the ultimate authority for interpreting scripture is typically considered to rest with the entire faith community rather than with any single individual or institution. The collective discernment of the community, guided by the Holy Spirit, is valued as an important aspect of interpreting scripture within Aladura Christianity.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in many other Christian denominations, there is often a select group of individuals who are trained and entrusted with the task of transmitting and teaching the scriptures to others. These individuals include clergy, pastors, ministers, evangelists, and teachers who have received formal training in biblical interpretation, theology, and pastoral ministry. These trained individuals play a significant role in transmitting the scriptures by preaching sermons, leading Bible studies, teaching Sunday school classes, conducting discipleship programmes, and providing pastoral care to members of the congregation. They are often recognised as spiritual leaders within the community and are entrusted with the responsibility of effectively communicating the teachings of the Bible to others.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in other Christian denominations, there is a codified canon of scriptures that is recognized as authoritative and inspired by God. The canon refers to the collection of books that are considered to be part of the Bible and are accepted as scripture within the religious community. The canon of scripture typically includes both the Old Testament and the New Testament. The Old Testament contains writings that are sacred to both Judaism and Christianity, including the Torah (the first five books of the Hebrew Bible), historical narratives, wisdom literature, and prophetic writings. The New Testament contains writings that focus on the life, teachings, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ, as well as the early Christian church.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the presence of monumental religious architecture varies depending on the specific denomination, congregation, and cultural context within the religious community. Unlike some other Christian denominations that may emphasise the construction of large cathedrals or churches as symbols of religious authority and prestige, Aladura Christianity often places greater emphasis on the spiritual and communal aspects of worship than on elaborate architectural structures. That said, there are Aladura Christian congregations and denominations that have constructed churches and other religious buildings that may be considered significant within their communities. These structures may vary in size and architectural style, ranging from simple and modest buildings to larger complexes with notable architectural features.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 75

Notes: It is a very challenging thing for one to provide a precise percentage for the area taken up by all religious monuments in the average settlement within Aladura Christianity, as this varies significantly depending on factors such as the size of the settlement, the density of religious institutions and local land use patterns. In many settlements, particularly smaller ones or those in rural areas, the area taken up by religious monuments is usually relatively modest compared to other land uses. This includes churches, prayer halls, or other religious buildings that serve the local Aladura Christian community. In such cases, the percentage of area taken up by religious monuments is usually relatively low. However, in larger settlements or urban areas where there is a higher concentration of religious institutions and a larger population, the area taken up by religious monuments is usually more substantial. This includes larger churches buildings, children auditorium, conference centres as well as associated facilities such as parking lots, community centres, or administrative buildings. In these cases, the percentage of area taken up by religious monuments is usually higher.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 1000

Notes: The size of the largest single religious monument in terms of square meters within Aladura Christianity varies greatly depending on factors such as location, purpose, and resources available for construction. In some cases, particularly in larger urban centres or areas with significant financial resources, the largest single religious monument varies from moderate sized cathedrals to expansive cathedrals or church complexes with a substantial footprint, potentially covering several hundred square meters. These monumental structures usually include expansive worship halls, chapels, administrative buildings and other facilities. However, in smaller towns or rural areas where resources are more limited, the largest religious monument is usually more modest in size. It could be a smaller church building or prayer hall, covering a few scores square meters or less.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 50

Notes: The height of religious monuments varies widely based on factors such as architectural design, cultural significance and available resources. In some cases, particularly in larger urban centres or areas with significant financial resources, religious monuments such as cathedrals or

churches have towering spires or domes that reach considerable heights. These structures can sometimes reach 50 meters in height. However, in smaller towns or rural areas where resources are more limited, religious monuments are usually more modest in height. They consist of smaller churches, chapels, or prayer halls with lower ceilings and simpler architectural features.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 15

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 15

Notes: Based on general observations, the average height of a religious monument within the context of Aladura Christianity ranges from a few meters to perhaps around 15 meters, but this can vary significantly depending on local circumstances and architectural preferences.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 65

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, there are various types of religious monumental architecture found within Aladura Christianity, as well as in other religious traditions. These architectural styles varies based on factors such as geographical location, cultural influences, historical context, and theological beliefs.

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, tombs are often present within the context of Aladura Christianity, serving as places of burial for deceased members of the religious community. These tombs vary in size, design, and significance, depending on factors such as cultural traditions, religious beliefs, and the social status of the deceased. In some cases, tombs may be simple and modest, consisting of basic graves or burial plots marked with gravestones or markers. These graves may be located within churchyards, cemeteries, or other designated burial grounds associated with Aladura Christian congregations. In other instances, particularly for individuals of prominence or importance within the religious community, more elaborate tombs or mausoleums may be constructed. These tombs can feature architectural embellishments, such as decorative carvings, inscriptions, or religious symbols, and may be situated within churches, cathedrals, or specially designated areas within burial grounds. The presence of tombs within Aladura Christianity reflects the belief in the importance of honouring and remembering the deceased, as well as the Christian belief in the resurrection of the dead and the hope of eternal life. Tombs serve as tangible reminders of the lives and legacies of those who have passed away and provide spaces for mourning, commemoration, and spiritual reflection within the religious community.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, cemeteries are commonly found within the context of Aladura Christianity, serving as designated burial grounds for deceased members of the religious community. Cemeteries provide consecrated spaces for the interment of the deceased and play an important role in the religious and cultural practices surrounding death and burial. Cemeteries associated with Aladura Christian congregations vary in size and design, ranging from small churchyards adjacent to churches or chapels to larger municipal or communal cemeteries. These burial grounds may be located in urban, suburban, or rural areas, depending on the needs and preferences of the local community. Within cemeteries, individual graves or burial plots are typically marked with gravestones, markers, or other commemorative plaques that identify the names, dates of birth and death, and sometimes religious affiliations of the deceased. These markers also include religious symbols or inscriptions reflecting the beliefs and faith traditions of the deceased or their families.

↳ Temples:

– No

Notes: The term "temple" is not commonly associated with Aladura Christianity, various types of religious buildings exist within the religious community to facilitate worship, prayer, and spiritual activities. These buildings vary in architectural style, size, and purpose, but they typically serve as sacred spaces for communal gatherings, religious ceremonies, and spiritual growth within the Aladura Christian tradition.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, altars are commonly found within the context of Aladura Christianity, serving as focal points for worship, prayer, and religious rituals within churches, chapels, and other religious buildings. The altar holds significant symbolic and spiritual importance within the religious tradition and is often regarded as a sacred space where believers can come into the presence of God. In Aladura Christian churches and chapels, the altar is typically a raised platform or table-like structure located at the front of the sanctuary or worship space. It is often adorned with religious symbols, candles, and other ceremonial items that enhance the sacred atmosphere of the space. The altar may also be draped with liturgical fabrics or cloths in accordance with the liturgical season or special occasions within the church calendar.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: Devotional markers, also known as religious or devotional objects, are items that hold significance within religious practices and rituals. While the term "devotional markers" may not be commonly used, various religious objects and symbols like crosses, scriptures, holy water, candles, and icons are present within the context of Aladura Christianity, serving as aids to devotion, prayer, and spiritual reflection.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: In the context of Aladura Christianity, mass gathering points include various types of spaces that are designated for communal worship, prayer, and religious gatherings. While these spaces may not always be permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures in the same way as public plazas or squares, they often serve similar functions as places where believers come together for collective worship and spiritual activities.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Prayer mountains, Mercy Ground (Ile Anu) and so on.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

– All public spaces

Notes: Iconography is present in people since some individuals wear religious icons or symbols, such as crosses or pendants depicting saints, as personal expressions of faith. It is also found at home, with many adherents of Aladura Christianity displaying religious icons, artwork, or symbols in their homes as expressions of devotion and reminders of their faith. Moreover, it is found in religious public spaces, as it is prominently displayed within religious public spaces such as churches, chapels, or prayer halls, where it serves as a focal point for worship and spiritual reflection. Furthermore, in regions where Aladura Christianity is prevalent, religious iconography is also present in some public spaces, such as community centres, schools, or hospitals associated with religious institutions. Nevertheless, while religious iconography is not present in all public spaces, it is still encountered in certain contexts where religious influence or symbolism is significant, such as religious festivals, processions, or cultural events.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, iconography incorporates depictions of supernatural beings, including zoomorphic representations that blend human and animal

characteristics. While the use of zoomorphic imagery is not as prevalent or standardised as in some other religious traditions, such as certain African indigenous religions, it is still encountered in Aladura Christian artwork and symbolism. For example, angels are celestial beings often depicted in Christian iconography as possessing both human and animal-like features. While angels are typically portrayed with human-like forms, they are also depicted with wings, halos, or other zoomorphic attributes, symbolising their divine nature and transcendent qualities. Cherubim and seraphim are specific types of angels described in the Bible, often depicted with multiple wings and other zoomorphic features. In Aladura Christian iconography, these angelic beings are represented in artwork and religious symbolism, serving as messengers of God's presence and glory.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in many Christian traditions, iconography incorporates depictions of supernatural beings with geomorphic characteristics, which blend human forms with elements of the natural world. While the use of geomorphic imagery is not as prevalent or standardised as in some other religious traditions, such as certain indigenous beliefs, it is still encountered in Aladura Christian artwork and symbolism. In Aladura Christian iconography, images of Jesus Christ and his topical reflections and teachings have been portrayed with geomorphic representations. His teaching about the different soils on which a sower planted has geomorphic implications. His encounters with the rivers and seas in ancient Israel are also symbolic of this subject matter. His various travels on foot, in canoes, and sudden appearances in locations of interest to him and his disciples speak to geomorphic representations in his ministry as well.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, iconography incorporates depictions of supernatural beings with anthropomorphic characteristics, which resemble human forms but possess divine or spiritual attributes. These beings are often depicted in religious artwork and symbolism to convey theological concepts, spiritual truths, and narratives from sacred texts. Central to Aladura Christian iconography is Jesus Christ, who is often portrayed as an anthropomorphic figure reflecting both his divine and human nature. In some Aladura churches, Christ is depicted in various poses and gestures, such as teaching, blessing, or performing miracles, to convey his role as Saviour, Teacher and Redeemer.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in many religious traditions, iconography includes depictions of supernatural beings in abstract or symbolic forms. These abstract symbols represent spiritual concepts, divine attributes, or cosmic forces within the religious worldview. While not as common or standardised as anthropomorphic or zoomorphic representations, abstract symbols play a significant role in conveying theological themes and spiritual truths.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity iconography include portrayals of the afterlife which depict beliefs and concepts related to what happens to individuals after death. These depictions often draw upon theological teachings, scriptural narratives, and cultural traditions within the religious group.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: In the iconography of Aladura Christianity, various aspects of doctrine are represented through symbolic imagery and visual motifs. These symbols serve to convey key theological concepts, doctrines, and beliefs within the religious tradition. While not as elaborate or standardised as in some other Christian denominations, Aladura Christian iconography includes the following distinct features related to aspects of doctrine: crosses, prophetic symbols, messianic symbols and so on.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in the iconography of Aladura Christianity, depictions of humans play a significant role. These representations include various individuals, such as biblical figures, saints, prophets, and ordinary believers, as well as symbolic representations of humanity in general. They often have iconography of their founders and leaders, like Samuel Bilewu Oshoffa for the Celestial Church of Christ, Moses Orimolade Tunolase for the Cherubim and Seraphim Church, Joseph Ayodele Babalola for the Christ Apostolic Church and so on.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, there are specific sites that are considered sacred or dedicated to sacred practice within the religious tradition. These sites include churches, prayer grounds, pilgrimage sites, and locations associated with significant events or spiritual experiences in the history of the faith. They also make use of the mausoleums of some of their founders, like Moses Orimolade, Joseph Ayodele Babalola and so on.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in Aladura Christianity, sacred sites are often oriented toward or associated with specific environmental features, reflecting the religious tradition's reverence for the natural

world and its recognition of the divine presence in creation. For example, we have forests, mountains, riversides, or coastal areas, which are revered for their beauty, tranquility, and spiritual significance. These natural settings provide adherents with a sense of connection to the earth and the divine, fostering contemplation, prayer, and communion with God. Sacred sites are located near water sources such as rivers, springs, or lakes, which are considered symbols of purity, life, and renewal within the religious tradition. Adherents gather at these water sources for baptismal ceremonies, spiritual cleansing rituals, or symbolic acts of devotion, recognising the sacredness of water as a gift from God.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, pilgrimages are present within Aladura Christianity, where believers undertake journeys to sacred sites or locations associated with spiritual significance as acts of devotion, prayer, and seeking divine intervention. These pilgrimages serve as opportunities for believers to deepen their faith, seek spiritual blessings, and experience communal solidarity with fellow believers.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: This varies depending on factors such as cultural context, individual beliefs, and the specific pilgrimage tradition or practice being observed. Generally, pilgrimage within Aladura Christianity is characterised by a sense of devotion, reverence, and commitment to spiritual journeying but the level of strictness differs among believers and communities.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Members of Aladura Christianity believe, just as most Christians do, that at death, the soul is separated from the body and survives in a conscious or unconscious disembodied state, but on the future Day of Judgment, souls will be re-embodied (whether in their former but now transfigured earthly bodies or in new resurrection bodies) and will live eternally in the heavenly kingdom. Even though Aladura Christianity originated from the Yoruba landscape, and with the knowledge of the Yoruba culture, this spirit-body distinction is clearly stated and in line with the major Christian beliefs.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of Spirit-mind is indeed distinct and central to their beliefs. This spiritual perspective emphasises the power of prayer and divine healing, rejecting

traditional medicines in favour of faith-based practices. The Spirit-mind is seen as a conduit for divine power and communication, often associated with visions, prophecies, and revelations, which are integral to the worship and healing methodologies of the Aladura churches.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of Spirit-mind is indeed central. It is viewed as non-material and ontologically separate from the physical body, reflecting a belief system that emphasises spiritual experiences and divine healing over material existence. This perspective aligns with the movement's focus on prayer, prophecy, and revelations, which are considered crucial for connecting with the divine and for personal and communal transformation.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Aladura Christianity, while focusing on solutions to earthly challenges, also upholds the Christian doctrine of life after death, reflecting a holistic approach to spirituality that addresses both present and eternal concerns.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group believes the spatial location of the afterlife is up in heaven. They often use the Yoruba word "Orun" to qualify this spatial location where the believers in Christ will go after their death on Earth.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: This specified realm of space is in heaven; the place where they often use the Yoruba word "orun" to describe. Most times, they usually talk about this place being the everlasting home for those of them who die believing in Jesus Christ.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: Even though Aladura Christianity believes in heaven as the place for their afterlife, this place is usually in a vaguely defined "above" space. They do not know the particular place where this heaven is located. What they know is that it is up there in the sky.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity does not have any belief in the afterlife in a vaguely defined "below" space.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity does not have any belief in the afterlife in a vaguely defined horizontal space.

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity does not have any belief in an afterlife in a vaguely defined "other" space. There is no other space apart from heaven.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity does not believe in the concept of reincarnation. They believe that once a person dies, they are bound to face judgment. It is very rare for one to see this religious group talk about anything related to reincarnation. Although most of their members are from the Yoruba ethnic group, they do not allow the Yoruba belief in the concept of reincarnation to foreshadow their Christian belief, which stipulates that judgment follows immediately after death.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: There are no special treatments for adherents' corpses. Once an adherent dies, the family is allowed to decide on whatever will happen to the corpse.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Co-sacrifices in a deceased's tomb or burial ground vary in significance across cultures and historical contexts. In the case of Aladura Christianity, such rituals are absent from their tombs or burial sites, as the religious group focuses on faith healing and prophecy rather than traditional sacrificial practices. While individual beliefs within the group often vary due to cultural influences, the official stance of Aladura Christianity does not endorse co-sacrifices. This distinction is crucial to understanding the practices and beliefs of Aladura Christians.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: The practice of including grave goods does not align with the typical Christian doctrine, which traditionally does not include such practices. Aladura Christianity emphasises prayer and healing, drawing on both Christian and African cultural values. While the incorporation of cultural values is evident in Aladura practices, the use of grave goods is not commonly associated with their burial

traditions. Instead, the focus is on spiritual aspects rather than physical offerings in the afterlife. This reflects a broader trend within Christianity, where grave goods are generally not a part of the burial customs.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, while formal burial practices are not universally standardised across all Aladura churches, many of these churches blend Christian beliefs with traditional African customs. This includes formal burial rites that respect both the Christian faith and the cultural heritage of the community. It is important to note that practices often vary significantly from one Aladura congregation to another, reflecting the dynamic and diverse nature of this Christian tradition in Africa.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: While formal burial practices within Aladura Christianity are not extensively documented, the movement's syncretic nature suggests a possible incorporation of traditional African customs alongside Christian rites. Cenotaphs, which are monuments erected in honour of a person whose remains are elsewhere, are not a commonly reported feature in Aladura burials. However, given the diversity of practices within Aladura churches, local customs often influence the presence of such memorials.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: While formal burial practices within Aladura Christianity are not extensively documented, it is understood that they blend traditional African customs with Christian rites. This syncretism often includes formal burials, which often take place in cemeteries, reflecting the movement's integration of indigenous cultural values with their Christian faith. As with many religious practices, specifics often vary widely among different congregations and regions.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: While Aladura Christianity diverged from Western religious practices, it maintained a Christian framework. Regarding burials, Aladura practices vary, but they generally include formal burial rites. The use of family tombs or crypts would depend on individual family traditions and the resources available to them. In many Christian traditions, including those influenced by Aladura beliefs, the concept of a final resting place is treated with respect and significance, often incorporating elements like crypts, which are below-ground chambers, or mausoleums (Joseph Ayodele Babalola is famous to have been buried in this place), which are above-ground structures.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, cultural values and religious practices often intertwine. While formal burials are a part of Christian tradition, the Aladura churches have been known to incorporate African cultural values into their practices. However, the specific practice of domestic burials, where individuals are interred within the home or in areas of daily life, is not widely documented in the available literature on Aladura Christianity. It is important to note that burial practices vary widely even within the same religious group, influenced by local customs, the environment, and individual preferences.

Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Mausoleum

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief in supernatural beings is deeply ingrained, reflecting the broader Christian understanding of spiritual entities beyond the physical realm. At the core of this belief system is the acknowledgement of one God, considered the Creator and Ruler of the universe. This deity is worshipped as omnipotent, omniscient, and omnipresent, embodying qualities of love, mercy, justice, and holiness. God serves as the ultimate source of life and existence, revered and prayed to by believers in Aladura Christianity as the focal point of their faith and devotion. Alongside God, Aladura Christianity acknowledges the existence of angels, celestial beings believed to serve as messengers, guardians, and servants of the divine. These beings are perceived as benevolent and powerful entities, carrying out divine tasks and ministering to the needs of believers. Angels are often associated with manifestations of divine presence, guidance, protection, and intervention in human affairs, serving as intermediaries between humanity and the divine realm. The Holy Spirit holds a central place in the belief system of Aladura Christianity, being regarded as the third person of the Trinity, alongside God the Father and God the Son (Jesus Christ). The Holy Spirit is understood as the divine presence and power at work in the world, inspiring and empowering believers for spiritual life and ministry. Believers rely on the guidance, indwelling, and empowerment of the Holy Spirit in their daily lives and spiritual practices, viewing this entity as essential for spiritual growth and communion with God. Conversely, the existence of malevolent spiritual beings, often referred to as demons, is also acknowledged within Aladura Christianity. These entities are believed to oppose God and seek to harm humanity through temptation, sin, sickness, and spiritual bondage. Believers engage in spiritual warfare against demonic forces, relying on prayer, fasting, and the power of God to resist and overcome their influence. Additionally, some branches of Aladura Christianity practice ancestor veneration, honouring deceased ancestors as spiritual intermediaries capable of interceding on behalf of the living. Prophets, apostles, and spiritual leaders are also esteemed within the tradition, viewed as human instruments through which divine revelation and guidance are communicated. Overall, the belief in supernatural beings within Aladura Christianity shapes believers' understanding of the spiritual realm and informs their practices, rituals, and worldviews.

A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Aladura Christianity, like mainstream Christianity, affirms belief in the existence of one God who is understood as the Creator, Sustainer, and Ruler of the universe. God is viewed as all-in-all, omnipotent, omniscient, and omnipresent, possessing attributes of kindness, love,

goodness, mercy, justice, and holiness and so on. Believers in Aladura Christianity worship and pray to God as the ultimate source of all life and existence.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of the Supreme High God is not necessarily anthropomorphic in the traditional sense of having a human-like form or appearance. Instead, the Supreme High God is often understood in theological terms as a transcendent and ineffable being beyond human comprehension. While believers may use anthropomorphic language and imagery to describe and relate to God, such as referring to God as a loving father or a righteous judge, these descriptions are understood as metaphorical expressions rather than literal representations of God's essence.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of a supreme high god being a sky deity is very common across many cultures and religions throughout history, most especially Aladura Christianity. This is as a result of their affinity with the indigenous culture. More importantly, the vastness and power of the sky have inspired awe and wonder since the beginning of humanity. It is a constant presence, associated with powerful natural phenomena like lightning, thunder, rain, and the sun.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of the Supreme High God is not typically associated with being chthonic, meaning of or relating to the underworld. Instead, the Supreme High God is understood as a transcendent and omnipresent being who is sovereign over all aspects of existence, including both the earthly realm and the spiritual realm.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of the Supreme High God is not typically fused with a monarch or earthly ruler in the same way as in certain ancient religious traditions, where kings or rulers were sometimes deified or considered divine. Instead, the Supreme High God is understood as a transcendent and sovereign being who surpasses all earthly authorities and human categories.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the relationship between earthly monarchs or rulers and the Supreme High God is not typically characterised as one of direct manifestation or emanation, as seen in certain theological concepts within other religious traditions.

Instead, while some believers may recognise the authority of earthly leaders as appointed or ordained by God, they generally understand this relationship within the framework of divine providence or God's sovereignty rather than as a direct manifestation of the Supreme High God.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of the Supreme High God is not typically understood in terms of kin relations with earthly elites or rulers. While some religious traditions may incorporate familial or kinship language to describe the relationship between deities and human rulers, such as referring to kings as "sons of God" or "divine descendants," Aladura Christianity generally emphasises the transcendence and sovereignty of the Supreme High God above human distinctions and relationships.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: Within Aladura Christianity, the Supreme High God is regarded as the ultimate source of all authority and wisdom. The Supreme High God does not have another type of loyalty connection with elites. However, some adherents often believe that God appoints or raises leaders according to His divine will and purposes and that earthly elites are called to serve their communities with humility and righteousness. This understanding of divine guidance and accountability often shapes adherents' attitudes toward leadership and governance.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the Supreme High God is indeed understood as unquestionably good. The belief in the inherent goodness and righteousness of God is a fundamental tenet of the faith, reflecting the character and nature of the divine as revealed in scripture and tradition. Believers in Aladura Christianity affirm that the Supreme High God is morally perfect, possessing attributes such as love, compassion, justice, mercy, and holiness. God's goodness is seen as the foundation of all creation and the source of all that is righteous and just in the world. The concept of God's goodness is central to the religious worldview of Aladura Christianity, shaping believers' understanding of divine providence, salvation, and ethical living. Believers trust in God's goodness as they navigate the challenges and uncertainties of life, relying on God's guidance and provision in times of need.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Omnipotence, omniscience, omnipresence, holiness, love and compassion, immutability and so on

Notes: The Supreme High God in Aladura Christianity is understood to possess a combination of attributes that reflect His transcendence, sovereignty, and moral perfection. These features shape believers' understanding of the divine and inform their worship, devotion, and ethical behavior.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in Aladura Christianity, the Supreme High God is believed to have knowledge of this world. The concept of God's omniscience, or complete knowledge and understanding of all things, is a fundamental tenet of the faith. This includes knowledge of the physical world, human affairs, and the thoughts and actions of individuals.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief in the Supreme High God's knowledge is typically not restricted to a particular domain of human affairs. Instead, God's omniscience is understood to encompass all aspects of existence, including but not limited to human affairs.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of the Supreme High God's knowledge being restricted to specific areas within a sample region is not a common belief. Instead, the Supreme High God is generally understood to possess omniscience, meaning complete knowledge and understanding of all things, without limitations based on geographic boundaries or specific domains.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of the Supreme High God's knowledge being unrestricted within a sample region is a common belief. The Supreme High God is generally understood to possess complete knowledge and understanding of all things, without limitations based on any geographical locations, boundaries, or specific domains.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief in the Supreme High God's knowledge being unrestricted outside of a sample region aligns with the broader understanding of God's omniscience. According to this belief, the Supreme High God possesses complete knowledge and understanding of all things, transcending geographic boundaries and limitations. Believers in Aladura Christianity typically affirm that the Supreme High God's knowledge extends beyond specific regions or domains, encompassing all aspects of existence,

regardless of location. This belief reflects the understanding of God as the ultimate source of wisdom, guidance, and providence, whose knowledge is not constrained by earthly limitations.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief in the Supreme High God's omnipresence and omniscience typically includes the understanding that God can perceive individuals everywhere, including in public spaces where they are normally visible. This concept aligns with a broader understanding of God's transcendence and presence in all aspects of existence. Believers in Aladura Christianity generally affirm that the Supreme High God is not limited by physical barriers or human limitations, such as time or space. Instead, God is understood to be present everywhere simultaneously, aware of all that occurs, including individuals' actions and circumstances in public settings.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Aladura Christianity often emphasises the omnipresence of God, showing that the supreme High God is indeed all-seeing and can observe believers in every place and situation, whether it be in the dark or at home. This concept aligns with many Christian denominations that hold the view of God as an omnipresent being, witnessing and involved in the lives of the faithful.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, belief in the Supreme High God's omniscience typically includes the understanding that God can perceive the innermost thoughts, desires, and motives of individuals, even those that are hidden from others. This concept aligns with a broader understanding of God's transcendence and knowledge of all aspects of existence. Believers in Aladura Christianity generally affirm that the Supreme High God is not only aware of outward actions and behaviours but also has insight into the deepest recesses of the human heart and mind. God is understood to be able to discern hidden motives, intentions, and attitudes, providing a level of understanding and accountability beyond human comprehension.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the Supreme High God is understood to be omniscient, possessing complete knowledge of all things, including the personal essence or character of each individual. This belief is consistent with many Christian denominations, which hold that God is all-knowing and intimately aware of the hearts and minds of people. The Aladura churches

emphasise personal piety and spirituality, often focusing on divine healing, prophetic revelations, and the power of prayer. As such, the relationship between the adherents and the divine is seen as direct and personal, with God being fully aware of the individual characteristics and needs of the followers. This connection is often expressed through prayer, worship, and spiritual experiences that are central to the Aladura faith practice.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of the Supreme High God is central to their beliefs. This movement holds that God provides practical guidance through the Holy Spirit. While the specific doctrines can vary among the different Aladura churches, the belief in the efficacy of prayer and the guidance of a living God is a common thread. As such, it is believed that God has foreknowledge of events and the lives of individuals, including their future actions. This aligns with many Christian denominations that attribute omniscience to God, acknowledging His ability to know all things, past, present, and future.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Understanding the intricacies of the natural world, the complexities of human relationships, and the dynamics of social, cultural, and political systems.

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the Supreme High God's knowledge of the world typically encompasses various aspects beyond those already mentioned. This knowledge includes understanding the intricacies of the natural world, the complexities of human relationships, and the dynamics of social, cultural, and political systems. Believers in Aladura Christianity often attribute to God a comprehensive knowledge that extends to every aspect of creation. This includes knowledge of the laws of nature, the functioning of ecosystems, and the interplay of environmental factors. It also includes awareness of human psychology, emotions, and behaviors, as well as insight into societal structures, institutions, and historical events. Furthermore, the Supreme High God is often seen as possessing wisdom and understanding that surpass human comprehension. This wisdom encompasses not only factual knowledge but also discernment, insight, and guidance in navigating the complexities of life. Believers turn to God's wisdom for direction, clarity, and discernment in making decisions and facing challenges.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief in the Supreme High God's deliberate causal efficacy in the world is often central to the understanding of divine providence and intervention. According to this belief, the Supreme High God actively engages with and influences the world, shaping events and outcomes according to divine will and purpose. Believers in Aladura Christianity typically affirm that the Supreme High God is

not merely a passive observer of human affairs but is actively involved in the unfolding of history and the lives of individuals. God's deliberate causal efficacy is seen in various ways, including answered prayers, miraculous interventions, and the working of providential events.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief in the Supreme High God's indirect causal efficacy in the world is often present, reflecting the understanding of God's sovereignty and providence. According to this belief, while the Supreme High God may not directly intervene in every event or circumstance, God's overarching influence and guidance are felt throughout creation. Adherents of Aladura Christianity typically affirm that the Supreme High God works through secondary causes, natural processes, and human agency to accomplish divine purposes in the world. This indirect causal efficacy may manifest in various ways, including answered prayers, providential circumstances, and the working of events in accordance with divine will. This belief in God's indirect causal efficacy underscores the understanding that God is actively involved in the unfolding of history and the lives of individuals, even if His presence is not always immediately apparent. Adherents trust in God's providence and sovereignty, knowing that all things ultimately work together for the good of those who love God.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that the Supreme High God exhibits positive emotions is central to the understanding of divine love, compassion, and care for humanity. According to this belief, the Supreme High God is not only a transcendent and sovereign being but also a personal and loving deity who is deeply invested in the well-being and welfare of His creation. Believers in Aladura Christianity often view God as a compassionate and merciful being who experiences positive emotions such as love, joy, and delight in relation to His creation. This understanding is rooted in sacred texts, teachings, and spiritual experiences that portray God's interactions with humanity in ways that evoke feelings of warmth, affection, and empathy.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that the Supreme High God exhibits negative emotions is not typically emphasized. Instead, the focus tends to be on God's attributes of love, compassion, mercy, and justice. However, some interpretations of divine texts or theological perspectives may acknowledge instances where God expresses anger or

sorrow in response to human disobedience or injustice. While the concept of God's negative emotions may not be a central focus in Aladura Christianity, believers generally understand that God's actions are guided by divine wisdom and justice. Even if there are references to God expressing negative emotions in certain contexts, they are often interpreted within the broader framework of God's overarching love and desire for humanity's well-being.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that the Supreme High God possesses physical attributes or needs such as hunger is typically emphasised. Though, the focus tends to be on God's attributes of transcendence, omnipotence, and spiritual perfection, there is a place given to show that God is indeed hungry for human praise. Believers in Aladura Christianity generally understand the Supreme High God as a divine and spiritual being who wants them to praise Him in songs, worship, and devotion, not minding the fact that He is not bound by human limitations or bodily needs nor is He seen as beyond the constraints of physical existence, existing outside of time and space.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the worship of supernatural beings other than the Supreme High God is generally not permissible. The faith emphasizes monotheism, the belief in one God, and views the Supreme High God as the ultimate source of authority, power, and worship. While Aladura Christianity acknowledges the existence of spiritual beings such as angels, saints, and other supernatural entities, their role is typically seen as subordinate to the Supreme High God. Believers are encouraged to direct their worship, prayers, and devotion solely to God and to recognize the unique status of the Supreme High God as the creator and sustainer of the universe.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Wisdom, holiness, immutability, mercy and compassion, providence and so on.

Notes: These features and attributes reflect the multifaceted nature of the Supreme High God within Aladura Christianity and shape believers' understanding of the divine and their relationship with the divine. They inspire reverence, awe, and devotion among believers, guiding them in their spiritual journey and daily lives.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that the Supreme High God communicates with the living is fundamental to the faith's understanding of divine guidance, revelation, and relationship with the divine. According to this belief, God interacts with believers through various means, providing guidance, instruction, and encouragement in their spiritual journey. Believers in Aladura Christianity often affirm that God communicates with them through prayer, meditation, sacred texts, dreams, visions,

and spiritual experiences. These forms of communication are seen as channels through which God imparts wisdom, insight, and direction to individuals and communities, guiding them in their faith and life decisions.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that the Supreme High God communicates with the living in waking, everyday life is central to the faith's understanding of divine guidance, presence, and relationship with believers. According to this belief, God is actively involved in the lives of individuals and communities, providing guidance, instruction, and encouragement through various means. Believers in Aladura Christianity often affirm that God communicates with them in their daily experiences, interactions, and circumstances. This communication may occur through inner promptings, intuition, and a sense of conviction, as well as through external signs, events, and encounters that are perceived as messages from God.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that the Supreme High God communicates with the living through dreams is significant and foundational to the faith's understanding of divine revelation, guidance, and interaction with believers. According to this belief, God can use dreams as a means of conveying messages, insights, and instructions to individuals on their spiritual journey. Believers in Aladura Christianity often view dreams as a sacred and meaningful aspect of their relationship with God. They believe that God can speak to them through the symbols, imagery, and narratives presented in dreams, providing guidance, encouragement, warnings, or revelations about future events.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that the Supreme High God communicates with the living through trance possession is recognised as a form of divine revelation and guidance. According to this belief, during trance possession, individuals may become vessels through which the divine communicates messages, guidance, or instructions to the community. Trance possession is often viewed as a sacred and profound spiritual experience within Aladura Christianity, where believers enter into a state of altered consciousness and allow themselves to be temporarily inhabited by spiritual entities, including the Holy Spirit or other divine beings. During this state, individuals may speak or act in ways that are believed to be influenced by the divine presence. Believers in Aladura Christianity interpret trance possession as a manifestation of God's power and presence, allowing for direct communication between the divine and the human realm. The messages conveyed during trance possession are often regarded as authoritative and are given careful consideration by the community.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: In some contexts of Aladura Christianity, believers indeed seek guidance from prophets or spiritual leaders to understand events and receive insights about their lives. These prophets or spiritual leaders are often believed to have a special gift of discernment or insight granted by the Supreme High God, which allows them to provide guidance and direction to the community. While this often involves practices that could be described as divination by some definitions, it is important to note that within Aladura Christianity, these practices are often understood and framed within the context of divine revelation rather than traditional divination. The emphasis is on seeking God's guidance and understanding through the spiritual gifts and insights granted to prophets and spiritual leaders, rather than relying on external methods or sources unrelated to the divine. Some believers approach prophets or spiritual leaders for counsel, prayer, and spiritual guidance, trusting in their ability to discern God's will and provide insights that are in alignment with divine principles and teachings. This relationship between believers and prophets reflects the belief in the importance of spiritual authority and discernment within the community.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that the Supreme High God communicates with the living only through religious specialists is not a predominant or widely accepted view. Instead, faith generally emphasises the direct relationship between individuals and God, encouraging believers to seek guidance, revelation, and communication with the divine through prayer, meditation, scripture, and personal spiritual experiences. While religious specialists such as prophets, pastors, or spiritual leaders may play important roles in providing guidance, teaching, and pastoral care within the community, they are not typically viewed as the exclusive intermediaries through which God communicates with believers. Instead, they are seen as facilitators or guides who assist believers in their spiritual journey and understanding of divine principles.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that the Supreme High God communicates exclusively through a monarch is not a typical or widely recognised view. Instead, the faith generally emphasises direct communication between individuals and God, without the need for intermediaries such as a monarch. While certain hierarchical structures or leadership roles exist within some branches or denominations of Aladura Christianity, they are not typically viewed as the sole channels through which God communicates with believers. Instead, leaders within the faith are often seen as spiritual guides or facilitators who help individuals deepen their understanding of divine principles and teachings.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Personal Experiences, intuition, community and fellowship and visions

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief in the Supreme High God's communication with the living can encompass various forms beyond those previously mentioned. While prayer, scripture, and spiritual leaders are often emphasised, believers may also perceive divine communication through personal experiences, intuition, and the natural world.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief in the presence of previously human spirits is not a central tenet of the faith. While the faith does acknowledge the existence of spiritual beings and the potential for communication with the divine realm, the emphasis is typically on the interaction between individuals and the Supreme High God, rather than on interactions with human spirits. Instead, Aladura Christianity tends to focus on concepts such as prayer, scripture, spiritual discernment, and guidance from religious leaders as means of communication with the divine. Believers also emphasise personal spiritual experiences, intuition, and the guidance of the Holy Spirit in their faith journey.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief in the presence of non-human supernatural beings is generally acknowledged. These beings may include angels, demons, and other spiritual entities that are believed to exist within the spiritual realm. While the faith primarily focuses on the worship of the Supreme High God and the guidance of the Holy Spirit, believers recognise the existence of other spiritual beings and their potential influence in the world. Angels are often viewed as messengers or servants of God who carry out divine tasks and provide protection and guidance to believers. They are seen as benevolent beings who act under God's will and assist believers in their spiritual journey. On the other hand, demons are perceived as malevolent entities that oppose God and seek to disrupt and harm humanity. Believers engage in spiritual warfare against demonic forces through prayer, fasting, and other spiritual practices aimed at resisting evil and seeking protection from negative influences.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that supernatural beings can be seen is not universal, and perceptions of spiritual experiences can vary among believers. While some individuals may report visions or encounters with supernatural beings, such as angels or demons, these experiences are typically understood as extraordinary and rare occurrences rather than commonplace.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that supernatural beings can be physically felt

is not uncommon among some believers. While experiences of sensing the presence or influence of supernatural beings such as angels or demons are reported by some individuals, they are generally understood as subjective and personal encounters rather than universally observable phenomena.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world is present, particularly concerning angels and demons. Angels, often considered messengers of God, are believed to possess knowledge of the earthly realm. They are thought to serve as intermediaries between the divine and human, carrying out tasks according to God's will, including delivering messages, providing protection, and offering guidance to believers. As such, they are believed to have knowledge about human affairs and events in this world. On the other hand, demons, considered malevolent spiritual beings opposed to God, are also believed to have knowledge of the world. They are thought to exploit this knowledge to sow discord, temptation, and chaos among humanity. In some interpretations, demons are believed to be aware of human weaknesses, struggles, and vulnerabilities, which they exploit in their efforts to lead individuals astray.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: In some interpretations within Aladura Christianity, there is a belief that non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, have knowledge restricted to particular domains of human affairs. For example, angels are believed to know divine purposes, spiritual matters, and God's plan for humanity. They possess insights into the spiritual realm, offer guidance on matters of faith, and intervene in situations according to God's will. However, their knowledge of mundane or earthly affairs is limited to the extent that it relates to their assigned tasks or missions. Conversely, demons are perceived as having knowledge primarily focused on exploiting human weaknesses, temptations, and vulnerabilities. They have insights into human desires, fears, and struggles, using this knowledge to deceive and manipulate individuals into sin or spiritual harm.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Within Aladura Christianity, beliefs about the knowledge of non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, vary among individuals and communities. While some interpretations suggest that these beings have knowledge restricted to specific areas within the sample region or geographical context, such beliefs are not universally held and are influenced by cultural and theological perspectives. In some interpretations, it is believed that angels and demons have knowledge limited to particular regions or domains within the earthly realm. For example, angels are perceived as having insight into spiritual

matters and divine purposes relevant to the local community or specific cultural context. Similarly, demons are thought to target particular areas or populations within the sample region, exploiting local customs, beliefs, and vulnerabilities.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Notes: Within Aladura Christianity, there is a range of beliefs regarding the knowledge of non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons. While some interpretations may suggest that their knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region, meaning they have comprehensive awareness of events, circumstances, and spiritual dynamics across the specified area, these beliefs are not universally held and may vary among individuals and communities. In interpretations where non-human supernatural beings are believed to have unrestricted knowledge within the sample region, they are often regarded as having omniscient or near-omniscient awareness of human affairs, spiritual matters, and the state of the world. This unrestricted knowledge may encompass various aspects of life, including individuals' thoughts, actions, intentions, and spiritual conditions.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Notes: Within Aladura Christianity, beliefs about the knowledge of non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, vary among individuals and communities. While some interpretations suggest that their knowledge is unrestricted outside of the sample region, meaning they have comprehensive awareness of events, circumstances, and spiritual dynamics beyond the specified area, these beliefs are not universally held and are often influenced by cultural, theological, and experiential factors.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, beliefs about the visibility and perception of non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, vary among individuals and communities. While some interpretations suggest that these beings can see individuals everywhere normally visible, including in public settings, such beliefs are not universally held and are influenced by cultural, theological, and experiential factors.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Notes: Beliefs regarding the visibility and perception of non-human

supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, vary within Aladura Christianity. While some interpretations suggest that these beings have the ability to see individuals everywhere, including in the dark and at home, such beliefs are not universally held and may depend on individual or cultural understandings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs regarding the ability of non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, to perceive the inner thoughts, emotions, and motivations of individuals vary within Aladura Christianity. While some interpretations suggest that these beings have the capacity to see inside the heart and mind, discerning hidden motives and intentions, such beliefs are not universally held and may depend on individual or cultural understandings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs regarding the ability of non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, to know human basic character (personal essence) vary within Aladura Christianity. While some interpretations suggest that these beings can see inside the heart and mind, discerning hidden motives and intentions, such beliefs are not universally held and may depend on individual or cultural understandings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs regarding the ability of non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, to know what will happen to individuals or to foresee future events vary within Aladura Christianity. While some interpretations suggest that these beings possess future sight or foreknowledge, such beliefs are not universally held and depend on individual or cultural understandings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: possess insights into spiritual realms, divine purposes, and cosmic truths

Notes: Beliefs about the knowledge of non-human supernatural beings within Aladura Christianity extend beyond conventional understandings of the physical world. These beings are often believed to possess insights into spiritual realms, divine purposes, and cosmic truths that surpass human comprehension. Their knowledge is not limited to mundane affairs but encompasses a deeper understanding of the spiritual fabric underlying existence.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs about the extent of the deliberate causal efficacy of non-human supernatural beings in the world vary within Aladura Christianity. While some interpretations suggest that these beings actively influence events and outcomes in the world, others may view their role as more limited or indirect. In some interpretations, non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, are believed to have deliberate causal efficacy, meaning they can directly intervene in worldly affairs to bring about specific outcomes. This perspective stems from theological understandings of their role as agents of divine will or as forces of spiritual influence.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs about the rewarding capabilities of non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and divine entities, within Aladura Christianity, vary. While some interpretations suggest that these beings can bestow rewards or blessings for virtuous behaviour, others view their role differently. In some interpretations, non-human supernatural beings are believed to have the authority to grant rewards for righteous deeds, acts of faithfulness, or adherence to divine principles. This perspective stems from theological understandings of divine grace, mercy, and spiritual blessings.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs about the punitive capabilities of non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, within Aladura Christianity vary. While some interpretations suggest that these beings have the ability to administer punishment or consequences for certain actions, others view their role differently. In some interpretations, non-human supernatural beings are believed to have the authority to mete out punishment for wrongdoing or disobedience to divine principles. This perspective stems from theological understandings of justice, divine judgment, and spiritual accountability.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs about the indirect causal efficacy of non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, within Aladura Christianity, vary. While some interpretations suggest that these beings exert influence on worldly affairs through indirect means, others may view their role differently. In some interpretations, non-human supernatural beings are believed to have indirect causal efficacy, meaning they can influence events and outcomes in the world through spiritual or unseen means. This perspective stems from theological understandings of spiritual warfare, divine providence, and the interplay between the spiritual and physical realms.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: While some interpretations suggest that these beings exhibit positive emotions, others may view their nature differently. In some interpretations, non-human supernatural beings are believed to exhibit positive emotions such as love, compassion, joy, and peace. This perspective stems from theological understandings of divine attributes, such as God's love for humanity and the benevolent nature of spiritual entities. However, the depiction of non-human supernatural beings and their emotional characteristics can vary among believers. Some may interpret their nature as transcending human emotions, while others anthropomorphize them to better understand their relationship with humanity.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: While some interpretations suggest that these beings exhibit negative emotions, others view their nature differently. In some interpretations, non-human supernatural beings are believed to exhibit negative emotions such as anger, jealousy, or wrath. This perspective stems from theological understandings of spiritual warfare, divine judgment, and the concept of evil forces opposing divine will. However, it is essential to note that beliefs about the emotional attributes of non-human supernatural beings vary widely among believers. Some interpret their nature as primarily embodying positive attributes, while others acknowledge the existence of negative emotions within the spiritual realm.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs about whether non-human supernatural beings, such as angels and divine entities, possess hunger vary within Aladura Christianity. While some interpretations suggest that these beings have needs or desires analogous to hunger, others view their nature differently.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Wisdom, power, or spiritual guidance

Notes: Beliefs about the characteristics and attributes of non-human supernatural beings within Aladura Christianity encompass a wide range of perspectives and interpretations. While some emphasise traditional attributes such as wisdom, power, or spiritual guidance, others incorporate unique or specific qualities based on cultural, theological, or experiential influences.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of mixed human-divine beings is not a prominent feature. The focus of the faith is typically on the relationship between humanity and the divine, with emphasis on spiritual growth, salvation, and the interaction between God and believers.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: Within Aladura Christianity, the concept of a variety of supernatural beings organised by kinship based on a family model is not a common feature. Instead, the focus tends to be more on the relationship between humanity and God, with angels and demons being the primary supernatural entities often discussed. These beings are typically not organised in a family structure but rather depicted as distinct entities with specific roles and attributes.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: While Aladura Christianity may acknowledge the significance of Archangel Michael and Angel Gabriel within the broader Christian tradition, the specific beliefs and practices related to these figures can vary among different branches or denominations within Aladura Christianity. Nonetheless, they are often regarded with reverence and may play important roles in spiritual beliefs and practices within the faith tradition. Those who believe in the ministry of angels often put these two angels in the top echelon while other like Angel Uriel an Angel Raphael are lower to them.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, beliefs about the power of supernatural beings, such as angels and demons, being domain-specific varies. While some interpretations suggest that these beings have specific domains or areas of influence in which their power is exercised, others view their capabilities more broadly or in a more nuanced manner. For example, some believers hold the view that certain angels are tasked with specific roles or responsibilities, such as protection, guidance, or messenger duties, and their power is focused within those domains. Similarly, some demons are believed to have particular areas of influence, such as temptation, spiritual warfare, or affliction, in which they exert their power.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of a pantheon, typically associated with polytheistic belief systems, is not a central feature. Instead, the focus of the faith is on monotheism, with belief in one supreme God. While there may be recognition of other spiritual beings such as angels and demons, they are typically understood within the framework of monotheism, serving as agents or messengers of the one God rather than as independent deities within a pantheon.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in Aladura Christianity, belief in supernatural monitoring is present. This belief encompasses the idea that supernatural beings, such as God, angels, and demons, are actively involved in monitoring human behaviour and influencing events in the physical and spiritual realms.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, belief in supernatural monitoring often extends to the adherence to prosocial norms, which are moral standards and behaviours that promote the well-being of others and society as a whole. This belief encompasses the idea that supernatural beings, such as God and angels, are actively engaged in observing and evaluating individuals' adherence to these norms.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Within Aladura Christianity, belief in the concern of supernatural beings, particularly God and angels, about taboos varies depending on cultural and theological interpretations within specific communities. However, the concept of supernatural beings caring about taboos aligns with broader religious frameworks that emphasise the importance of moral purity and obedience to divine commandments.

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief in supernatural beings, such as God and angels, caring about food taboos aligns with broader religious and cultural frameworks that emphasise dietary restrictions as a means of spiritual purity and obedience to divine commandments. However, beliefs about food taboos vary among different denominations and cultural contexts within Aladura Christianity.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that supernatural beings, such as God and angels, care about taboos related to sacred spaces aligns with the broader religious and cultural emphasis on the sanctity of certain places and the need for reverence and respect in their use. While beliefs about sacred spaces and associated taboos vary among denominations and cultural contexts within Aladura Christianity, adherents/believers often ascribe sacredness to specific places, such as churches, prayer rooms, altars, or pilgrimage sites. These spaces are believed to be consecrated

for religious worship, prayer, and spiritual activities, and are considered sanctuaries where believers can encounter the divine presence. Supernatural beings are believed to be present in these sacred spaces, and their care about taboos related to these spaces is tied to their sacredness. Also, some believers in Aladura Christianity typically view sacred spaces as venues for encountering the divine and seeking spiritual guidance, healing, and empowerment. As such, there are often rules or taboos associated with behaviour within these spaces, aimed at maintaining reverence, decorum, and holiness. Supernatural beings are believed to care about adherence to these taboos as a sign of respect for their presence and the sanctity of the space. In the same vein, taboos related to sacred spaces may also be connected to the concept of ritual purity within Aladura Christianity. Some believers believe that certain actions or behaviours can defile or desecrate sacred spaces, rendering them unfit for divine worship or spiritual activities. Supernatural beings are believed to be concerned with maintaining the ritual purity and sanctity of these spaces by enforcing taboos that govern their use.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that supernatural beings, such as God and angels, care about taboos related to sacred objects is consistent with the broader religious and cultural emphasis on the sanctity of certain items and the need for reverence and respect in their handling and use. For example, Aladura Christianity often ascribes sacredness to certain objects, such as religious artefacts, symbols, scriptures, or relics. These objects are believed to be imbued with spiritual significance and serve as conduits for divine presence, blessing, and protection. Supernatural beings are thought to be attentive to the treatment and handling of these sacred objects, and their care about taboos related to them is tied to their sacred nature.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Personal conduct, spiritual devotion, social justices and so on

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that supernatural beings, such as God and angels, care about various aspects of human behavior and religious practices extends beyond specific categories like sacred spaces or objects. Supernatural beings are believed to be concerned with a wide range of human activities, emotions, and moral conduct, reflecting the holistic nature of spiritual life within the tradition.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that supernatural beings, such as God and angels, care about the murder of coreligionists is consistent with broader religious and ethical principles that emphasise the sanctity of human life and the importance of justice, compassion, and community solidarity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that supernatural beings care about the murder of

members of other religions is consistent with broader religious and ethical principles that emphasise the sanctity of human life and the importance of justice, compassion, and community solidarity. The members of this religious group are not permitted to murder members of other religions whatsoever.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief that supernatural beings care about the murder of members of other polities is consistent with broader religious and ethical principles that emphasise the sanctity of human life and the importance of justice, compassion, and community solidarity. No one is allowed to murder anyone.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in many Christian religious traditions, the belief that supernatural beings care about sex reflects the broader cultural and ethical concerns surrounding human sexuality. Aladura Christianity typically promotes ethical principles regarding sexuality, emphasising chastity, fidelity within marriage, and respect for oneself and others. In one aspect, some believers view sexual behaviour as significant not only for its physical aspects but also for its moral and spiritual implications. On the other hand, supernatural beings are believed to care about adherence to these ethical standards and are perceived as guiding believers in their sexual conduct. Also, marriage is often regarded as a sacred institution within Aladura Christianity, with sexual relations intended for the context of marriage between a man and a woman. Supernatural beings are seen as being concerned with upholding the sanctity of marriage and promoting fidelity and commitment between spouses. Adultery or infidelity are viewed as violations of this sacred bond and subject to divine judgment.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings are often believed to care about adultery, viewing it as a violation of moral and ethical principles governing marital fidelity and sexual conduct. Adultery, which involves engaging in sexual relations with someone other than one's spouse, is typically considered a serious transgression within the tradition, with potential spiritual, moral, and social consequences.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings are often believed to care about incest, considering it a violation of moral, social, and religious norms. Incest, which involves sexual relations between close relatives, is typically viewed as a serious transgression with potential spiritual, moral, and social consequences.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: sexual abuse and trauma, LGBTQ

Notes: Aladura Christianity holds traditional views on gender and sexual identity, affirming heterosexual marriage and family structures. However, beliefs about sexual orientation and gender identity often vary among individuals and denominations within the tradition. Supernatural beings are believed to care about the experiences and identities of all individuals, offering love, acceptance, and support to those navigating questions of sexual orientation, gender identity, and expression.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings are often believed to care about lying, considering it a violation of moral and ethical principles governing truthfulness, integrity, and honesty. Lying, which involves deliberate deception or falsehood, is typically viewed as a serious transgression with potential spiritual, moral, and social consequences.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings are often believed to care about honoring oaths, considering them binding commitments made before divine authority and subject to moral and spiritual accountability. Honoring oaths, which involves fulfilling promises and obligations made in the presence of God or other sacred entities, is typically viewed as a matter of integrity, honesty, and faithfulness.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care about laziness, considering it a hindrance to personal growth, productivity, and spiritual development. Laziness, which involves a lack of diligence, effort, or motivation in fulfilling one's responsibilities and potential, is typically viewed as a character flaw with potential moral and social consequences. Aladura Christianity emphasises the value of diligence, industry, and stewardship in all aspects of life, including work, education, and spiritual practice. Laziness is seen as contrary to the principles of hard work and perseverance upheld by the tradition. Supernatural beings are believed to care about the cultivation of a strong work ethic, guiding believers in the pursuit of excellence and the fulfilment of their duties and obligations.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care about sorcery, viewing it as a form of spiritual manipulation, deception, and rebellion against divine authority. Sorcery, which involves the practice of magic, witchcraft, or occult rituals to influence or control natural and supernatural forces, is typically seen as a serious transgression with potential moral, spiritual, and social consequences.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting, advocating for peaceful conflict resolution, and the avoidance of violence whenever possible. Non-lethal fighting refers to situations where physical altercations occur without resulting in serious injury or death.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care about shirking risk, emphasising the importance of courage, faith, and trust in divine providence. Shirking risk refers to avoiding or evading challenges, uncertainties, or responsibilities due to fear, doubt, or a lack of confidence.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care about respecting elders, and recognising the importance of honoring wisdom, experience, and authority within the community. Disrespecting elders refers to behaviours or attitudes that undermine the dignity, authority, or contributions of older individuals.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care about gossiping, recognizing the harmful effects of spreading rumors, slander, or malicious talk within the community. Gossiping refers to the act of sharing or spreading information about others, often without their consent and with the intention of causing harm, stirring up conflict, or damaging reputations.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care about property crimes, recognising the importance of respecting the property rights and material possessions of others. Property crimes encompass a range of offenses such as theft, vandalism, trespassing, and destruction of property.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance, emphasising the importance of adhering to sacred traditions, ceremonies, and practices. Ritual observance involves the performance of religious rites, rituals, and ceremonies following established customs and teachings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care deeply about the performance of rituals, as rituals are seen as essential channels for connecting with the divine, seeking blessings, and expressing devotion. Rituals are believed to invite the presence of supernatural beings, creating a sacred space where believers can commune with the divine. Proper performance of rituals is seen as crucial for ensuring that the presence of God or other spiritual entities is invoked and honored. Supernatural beings are perceived as attentive to the sincerity, reverence, and authenticity of ritual practices, responding to the heartfelt prayers and offerings of believers.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care about the conversion of non-religionists, reflecting a desire for all individuals to embrace the faith and experience spiritual salvation. Aladura Christianity teaches that spiritual salvation is available to all humanity through faith in Jesus Christ and adherence to Christian teachings. Supernatural beings are believed to care deeply about the eternal destiny of every individual, desiring that none should perish but that all should come to repentance and faith. The conversion of non-religionists is seen as essential for their spiritual well-being and eternal salvation. Believers in Aladura Christianity often perceive themselves as bearers of a divine mandate to share the gospel message with others and make disciples of all nations. Supernatural beings are perceived as actively involved in the mission of evangelism, working through believers to bring about the conversion of non-religionists. The spread of the Christian faith is viewed as a fulfilment of God's redemptive purposes for humanity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings care about economic fairness, reflecting a concern for justice, equality, and the well-being of individuals and communities. Aladura Christianity upholds principles of justice and righteousness, emphasising the importance of fair treatment and equitable distribution of resources. Supernatural beings are believed to care about the economic conditions and opportunities available to individuals, ensuring that all have access to the necessities of life and opportunities for flourishing. Economic fairness is seen as aligned with divine principles of justice and compassion.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings do not have a direct concern for personal hygiene per se, but the principles of cleanliness and health are often emphasised within the context of spiritual and physical well-being. Aladura Christianity often promotes a holistic approach to health, recognising the interconnectedness of the physical, emotional, and spiritual dimensions of human life. While supernatural beings are not directly concerned with personal hygiene practices such as bathing or grooming, believers are encouraged to maintain good hygiene as part of their overall commitment to health and well-being.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Spiritual growth, community harmony, and so on.

Notes: Supernatural beings within the context of Aladura Christianity are perceived as having concerns beyond those directly related to personal hygiene, economic fairness, and the conversion of non-religionists.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural beings have the authority to mete out punishment as part of their role in administering justice and maintaining moral order. The concept of divine judgment and retribution is central to many religious traditions, including Aladura Christianity, where believers often understand supernatural beings as having the power to reward righteousness and punish wrongdoing.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the cause or agent of supernatural punishment is typically understood to be God. Believers in Aladura Christianity often attribute divine punishment to the actions of God in response to human disobedience, sin, or moral wrongdoing.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural punishment is often attributed to the actions of God, who is believed to be the ultimate authority and source of divine justice, and other supernatural beings who usually play their roles in spiritual matters, including conveying messages, interceding on behalf of believers, or carrying out specific tasks, the administration of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural punishment is often attributed to the actions of supernatural beings who usually play their roles in spiritual matters, including conveying messages, interceding on behalf of believers, or carrying out specific tasks.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the reason for supernatural punishment is often understood within the framework of divine justice and moral accountability. Believers generally attribute

supernatural punishment to the consequences of disobedience, sin, or moral wrongdoing.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the reason for supernatural punishment is not typically understood as being primarily aimed at enforcing religious ritual-devotional adherence. Instead, supernatural punishment is generally perceived within the context of divine justice and moral accountability. While adherence to religious rituals and devotional practices may be important aspects of the tradition, supernatural punishment is more commonly associated with consequences for moral transgressions, disobedience to divine commandments, or rebellion against God.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, supernatural punishment is not typically understood as being specifically aimed at enforcing group norms. Instead, it is generally perceived within the context of divine justice and moral accountability. While adherence to group norms and community standards may be important within the tradition, supernatural punishment is more commonly associated with consequences for individual moral transgressions, disobedience to divine commandments, or rebellion against God.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the belief is that supernatural punishment primarily serves to uphold divine justice and moral accountability, rather than specifically aiming to inhibit selfishness. While selfishness is considered a moral failing within the tradition, supernatural punishment is generally perceived as a consequence of individual moral transgressions, disobedience to divine commandments, or rebellion against God, rather than solely targeting selfish behaviour. Aladura Christianity teaches the importance of living a righteous and morally upright life, characterised by love for God and neighbour, humility, generosity, and compassion. While selfishness is viewed as incompatible with these values, supernatural punishment is not typically seen as a direct means of inhibiting selfishness. Instead, believers are encouraged to cultivate virtues such as selflessness, humility, and generosity through spiritual growth, ethical teachings, and personal reflection.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the reason for supernatural punishment is not typically perceived as being random. Instead, it is generally understood within the framework of divine justice and moral accountability. Believers in Aladura Christianity believe in a God who is just and righteous, and supernatural punishment is seen as a consequence of individual moral transgressions, disobedience to divine commandments, or rebellion against God's will.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in many Christian traditions, the concept of supernatural punishment typically includes the idea of consequences in the afterlife. Believers often hold that individuals are judged after death based on their actions and moral choices during their earthly lives. This judgment often results in rewards for the righteous and punishment for the unrepentant or sinful. Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are often depicted as the consequence of rejecting God's will, living a life of disobedience, or failing to seek forgiveness for one's sins. These punishments often include separation from God, described as spiritual death or eternal damnation, where individuals experience the absence of divine presence and are cut off from the blessings of heaven.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the emphasis on supernatural punishments in the afterlife often varies among different communities and interpretations of the faith. While the concept of consequences in the afterlife is a fundamental aspect of Christian theology, including Aladura Christianity, the degree of emphasis placed on supernatural punishments often differ depending on the teachings and beliefs of individual groups or leaders within the tradition. Some branches or denominations within Aladura Christianity often place a significant emphasis on the consequences of sin and the reality of supernatural punishment in the afterlife as a means of emphasising the importance of moral accountability and the need for repentance. This emphasis are reflected in sermons, teachings, and religious practices that underscore the seriousness of disobeying God's commandments and the urgency of seeking salvation. Other groups within Aladura Christianity adopt a more balanced approach, emphasising both the consequences of sin and the message of God's love, mercy, and forgiveness. While acknowledging the reality of supernatural punishment, these groups also highlight the hope of redemption and the possibility of reconciliation with God through faith in Jesus Christ.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in many Christian traditions, punishment in the afterlife is typically understood to be more severe than mild sensory displeasure. The concept of punishment in the afterlife often includes the idea of spiritual separation from God, described as spiritual death or eternal damnation, where individuals experience the absence of divine presence and are cut off from the blessings of heaven. The severity of supernatural punishment in the afterlife is often depicted as proportional to one's rejection of God's will, persistence in sin, or refusal to seek forgiveness. This punishment often involves various forms of suffering, including spiritual anguish, regret, and the realisation of being separated from God for eternity. While the exact nature of supernatural punishment in the afterlife varies among

different interpretations of Aladura Christianity, it is commonly understood to involve consequences that extend beyond mild sensory displeasure. The belief in divine justice and moral accountability emphasises the seriousness of sin and the eternal consequences of one's actions, underscoring the importance of living a righteous and obedient life in accordance with God's will.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in many Christian traditions, punishment in the afterlife is typically understood to be more severe and extreme sensory displeasure. The concept of punishment in the afterlife often includes the idea of spiritual separation from God, described as spiritual death or eternal damnation, where individuals experience the absence of divine presence and are cut off from the blessings of heaven. The severity of supernatural punishment in the afterlife is often depicted as proportional to one's rejection of God's will, persistence in sin, or refusal to seek forgiveness. This punishment may involve various forms of suffering, including spiritual anguish, regret, and the realisation of being separated from God for eternity. While the exact nature of supernatural punishment in the afterlife varies among different interpretations of Aladura Christianity, it is commonly understood to involve consequences that include extreme sensory displeasure. The belief in divine justice and moral accountability emphasises the seriousness of sin and the eternal consequences of one's actions, underscoring the importance of living a righteous and obedient life in accordance with God's will.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in many other Christian traditions, the concept of punishment in the afterlife typically does not involve reincarnation as an inferior life form. Instead, the belief centres around the idea of judgment, where individuals are held accountable for their actions during their earthly lives and experience either rewards or consequences in the afterlife based on their moral choices.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, as in many other Christian denominations, the concept of reincarnation is not a prominent belief. Instead, the tradition typically emphasises the finality of death and the belief in an afterlife where individuals face judgment for their actions during their earthly lives.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Within Aladura Christianity, supernatural punishments in this life are perceived as manifestations of God's corrective measures or disciplinary actions aimed at guiding believers back to the right path. These punishments could include various forms of adversity or challenges that individuals face as a consequence of their actions, disobedience, or departure from spiritual principles.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of punishment in this life is typically understood within the framework of divine discipline or corrective measures rather than mere "bad luck." While adversity or challenges are perceived as consequences of one's actions or disobedience to spiritual principles, the interpretation of such events goes beyond the notion of random misfortune. Instead, within the Aladura tradition, adverse circumstances or challenges in life are seen as opportunities for spiritual growth, learning, and transformation. Individuals view them as manifestations of divine discipline or correction aimed at guiding them back to the right path and fostering personal development. However, it is crucial to note that the interpretation of events as divine punishment or discipline varies among different individuals and communities within Aladura Christianity. Some attribute hardships or difficulties directly to divine intervention, while others view them through the lens of natural processes, human agency, or the complexities of life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, punishment in this life is generally understood within the framework of divine discipline or corrective measures rather than solely political failure. While political setbacks or failures often occur, they are typically interpreted within the broader context of spiritual principles and moral accountability.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, punishment in this life is generally understood within the framework of divine discipline or corrective measures rather than solely as defeat in battle. While defeat in battle occurs, it is typically interpreted within the broader context of spiritual principles and moral accountability.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, punishment in this life is generally understood within the framework of divine discipline or corrective measures rather than solely as crop failure or bad weather. While agricultural challenges such as crop failure or adverse weather conditions occur, they are typically interpreted within the broader context of spiritual

principles and moral accountability. Within the Aladura tradition, individuals often view crop failure or bad weather as part of the consequences of one's actions or disobedience to divine teachings. They often perceive them as opportunities for introspection, repentance, and alignment with spiritual principles rather than solely attributing them to natural phenomena. However, it is important to note that interpretations of events such as crop failure or bad weather often vary among different individuals and communities within Aladura Christianity. Some indeed see agricultural challenges as a form of divine discipline or a consequence of spiritual disobedience, while others attribute them to various environmental, agricultural, or socio-economic factors.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: While the belief in punishment through disasters on journeys is not a widely documented aspect of Aladura doctrine, the movement does stress the importance of moral living and divine retribution. It is important to note that the Aladura's practices and beliefs are diverse, with various sects interpreting doctrines in different ways.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: While the concept of punishment in the form of bad luck visited on descendants is not a universally accepted doctrine within Aladura Christianity, some adherents hold this belief. It is important to note that beliefs about punishment and misfortune vary widely even within a single religious tradition, and they are often influenced by a complex mix of theology, cultural practices, and individual interpretation.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of supernatural rewards in the afterlife is indeed significant and emphasised within the religious teachings and beliefs. While the tradition emphasises the importance of righteous living, obedience to divine commandments, and adherence to spiritual principles in this life, it also underscores the promise of supernatural rewards in the afterlife for those who remain faithful and

devoted to God. Within the Aladura tradition, supernatural rewards in the afterlife may include concepts such as eternal life, reunion with loved ones, spiritual bliss, and the enjoyment of divine blessings in the presence of God. These rewards serve as incentives for believers to persevere in their faith, endure trials and tribulations, and remain steadfast in their commitment to spiritual values and moral integrity. The emphasis on supernatural rewards in the afterlife provides believers with hope, encouragement, and motivation to live virtuously, seek spiritual growth, and strive for righteousness in their daily lives. It serves as a reminder of the ultimate purpose of human existence and the promise of divine fulfillment beyond the limitations of earthly existence.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of reward in the afterlife is not typically associated with reincarnation as a superior life form. Instead, the emphasis is often placed on more traditional Christian beliefs regarding the afterlife, such as eternal life in the presence of God, spiritual bliss, and communion with divine beings.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the emphasis on supernatural rewards in this life varies among different individuals and communities within the religious group. While some adherents place a significant emphasis on the belief in immediate blessings and supernatural interventions in their daily lives, others focus more on spiritual growth,

moral integrity, and long-term salvation.

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Messianic beliefs are indeed present in Aladura Christianity, though the specific nature and emphasis of these beliefs varies among different branches or denominations within the tradition. In general, messianic beliefs within Aladura Christianity centres around the belief in Jesus Christ as the Messiah, the anointed saviour prophesied in the Old Testament scriptures. Within Aladura Christianity, Jesus Christ is typically regarded as the fulfilment of Messianic prophecies, with believers placing their faith in his role as the redeemer and saviour of humanity. Messianic beliefs often include the expectation of Jesus' return in the future, as foretold in the New Testament scriptures.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the purpose of the Messiah, Jesus Christ, is generally understood to be multifaceted and central to the faith. While interpretations may vary among different branches or denominations within the tradition, several key aspects of the Messiah's purpose are commonly emphasised, like redemption, restoration, reconciliation, and judgment.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of the Messiah as a political figure who restores political rule is not as central as in some other religious traditions. While Jesus Christ is recognised as the Messiah and is believed to have a role in the establishment of God's kingdom, the emphasis is typically more on spiritual rather than political transformation.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, the concept of the Messiah as a priestly figure who restores religious traditions is not as prominent as in some other religious traditions. While Jesus Christ is recognised as a high priest in Christian theology, his role is often understood more broadly in terms of redemption, reconciliation, and the restoration of humanity's relationship with God.

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Establishment of God's Rule

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, eschatology, which is the theological study of the end times or the ultimate destiny of humanity and the world, is present in Aladura Christianity. Eschatological beliefs are central to the faith and often shape believers' understanding of the future and their role within it.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Aladura Christianity are to love God and others, to share the Gospel of Jesus Christ and to make disciples of all human beings. Also, they are expected to live a life of holiness and purity, to serve others, and to be good stewards of all that God has given them.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, beliefs about who will survive or endure the eschaton, or the final culmination of God's purposes for humanity and the world, typically align with traditional Christian teachings on judgment, salvation, and eternal life that only the righteous and those obedient to divine command will survive the eschaton.

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Only the in-group members who are righteous and those obedient to divine command will survive the eschaton.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, adherence to general social norms is often encouraged as a reflection of biblical principles and Christian ethics. While specific social norms vary depending on cultural context and denominational interpretations, there are certain overarching principles and values that are typically emphasised within the tradition.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, distinctions exist between conventional norms or practices and moral

values, although the exact nature of this distinction varies depending on cultural context and denominational interpretations.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: Aladura Christianity emphasises the moral norms that they believe are derived from universal principles of justice and fairness, while conventional norms apply to what is derived locally and are contingent upon rule and authority.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: These are ethical principles and standards that are based on religious teachings, particularly those found in the Bible. Moral values guide believers' behaviour and decision-making, shaping their understanding of right and wrong, good and evil. Examples include honesty, kindness, justice, and respect for others.

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, moral norms are often linked to theological or metaphysical concepts rooted in Christian beliefs. These moral norms are not merely arbitrary rules but are understood to be grounded in the character and will of God as revealed in Scripture.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, moral norms may indeed be explicitly linked to metaphysical entities, although the exact nature of these linkages varies based on interpretations within the tradition.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, moral norms are typically not explicitly linked to impersonal cosmic orders like karma, as this concept is more pronounced in Eastern religions such as Hinduism and Buddhism. Instead, moral norms are usually grounded in personalistic theological frameworks centred on the character and will of God, as revealed in Christian scripture and tradition. However, it is worth noting that some believers draw parallels between certain aspects of Christian theology and concepts found in other religious traditions, including ideas about moral cause and effect. While the specific terminology and philosophical underpinnings often differ, there are recognition of the consequences of moral actions and the principle of reaping what one sows. For example, believers in Aladura Christianity tend to emphasise the biblical concept of sowing and reaping, which is found in passages such as Galatians 6:7-9: "Do not be deceived: God cannot be mocked. A man reaps what he sows. Whoever sows to please their flesh, from the flesh will reap destruction; whoever sows to please the

Spirit, from the Spirit will reap eternal life."

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, moral norms are typically linked to anthropomorphic beings, specifically to the character, will, and teachings of God as revealed in Christian scripture.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, moral norms are often explicitly linked to the commands of an anthropomorphic being, namely God as understood within the Christian faith.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, moral norms typically have a special connection to the metaphysical realm, particularly through their grounding in the divine will and the spiritual dimensions of human existence. For example, believers in Aladura Christianity understand themselves to be morally accountable to God, who judges human actions according to his divine standards. adherence to God's moral norms is seen as a marker of faithfulness and obedience, while disobedience carries the risk of divine judgment and punishment.

↳ Moral norms apply to:

- All individuals within society
- All individuals within contemporary world
- All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, several virtues are commonly advocated as central to the religious life and moral conduct of believers. While the specific emphasis on virtues varies among different denominations and cultural contexts within the tradition, some key virtues typically promoted include faith, prayerfulness, humility, forgiveness, love, compassion and so on.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes

- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: This is a very important aspect that most denominations of Aladura Christianity emphasise. However, this is often in relation to the female gender. There is the belief that this gender, any time they are in their menstruation period, are unclean. Thus, they are to be made clean afterwards through purification. However, this belief is not universal as it is peculiar to denominations like the Celestial Church of Christ, some Cherubim and Seraphim Church and so on.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity does not generally require celibacy from its members. The movement, which emphasises prayer and spiritual healing, allows its adherents to marry and have families. Celibacy is not typically a condition for membership or participation in the religious practices of Aladura churches. These churches often reflect a blend of Christian beliefs with traditional African religious practices, adapting to the cultural values of the communities they serve.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Aladura Christianity requires some forms of sexual constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence) from its members. It is known for incorporating African cultural values and practices into

its expression of Christianity, which vary among different Aladura denominations.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: The group does not support same sex marriages among men neither does it support bestiality.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: The group does not support same sex marriages among women neither does it support bestiality.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity is known for its emphasis on prayer and healing, and do not require castration for membership. Instead, these churches focus on community, spirituality, and the incorporation of certain cultural practices into their worship. It is important to approach different religious practices with respect and understanding, recognising the diversity within Christian traditions globally.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, fasting is a significant spiritual practice that reflects the movement's emphasis on prayer and divine healing. The Aladura churches, which originated among the Yoruba people of Nigeria, often engage in fasting as part of their devotional activities. While fasting practices vary among different Aladura congregations, it is generally observed as a means to deepen spiritual connection and seek divine intervention and not a means to accepting others as their members.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity does not have specific dietary practices. While not all denominations have strict food taboos, some do observe fasting periods or abstain from certain foods as a form of spiritual discipline. In the case of Aladura, there is no widely documented mandate for food taboos similar to those found in other religions or denominations. However, individual practices vary, and some

members often choose to follow personal or communal dietary restrictions as part of their faith expression.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity emphasises prayer and healing without the need for permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations. The term 'Aladura' means 'praying people' in Yoruba, and the movement is known for its use of African symbols, traditional healing modalities, and worship styles that reflect the indigenisation of Christianity. Membership in Aladura churches does not involve practices that cause harm to the body, as they focus on spiritual solutions to this-world problems, including healing through prayer and the use of blessed water.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity emphasises prayer and healing rather than painful practices. The term 'Aladura' translates to 'praying people' in Yoruba, reflecting the group's focus on spiritual interventions and divine healing as opposed to physical rituals or self-harm. Membership in Aladura churches does not entail engaging in painful physical positions or receiving wounds; instead, it is characterised by a commitment to prayer, faith healing, and a moral code aligned with Christian principles.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity emphasises prayer, divine healing, and a puritanical moral code. The practices of Aladura churches generally reject traditional African religious rituals and do not require any form of adult sacrifice as part of their worship or membership requirements. Instead, they focus on spiritual practices such as prayer, fasting, and the use of holy water for healing.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity does not require child sacrifice as part of its practices. The movement is known for its emphasis on divine healing, prophetic revelations, and a puritanical moral code, rather than any form of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity does not require self-sacrifice in the form of suicide for its members. Instead,

it focuses on communal salvation and support, spiritual growth, and adherence to Christian teachings. The movement is known for its vibrant worship and the incorporation of African cultural values into its Christian faith.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Membership in Aladura Christianity does not involve the sacrifice of property or valuable items. The movement has a rich history of responding to societal issues through prayer and faith healing, distinguishing itself from other Christian denominations by its unique practices and beliefs.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Aladura Christianity places a strong emphasis on prayer and healing. Members are known as "praying people" and are expected to engage in regular prayer and attend worship services. While it does not bar laity members from joining the clergy ranks, it maintains a strict hierarchy among the clergy. Participation in the Aladura community typically involves a commitment of time to spiritual activities and communal gatherings.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity does not inherently require physical risk-taking as a condition for membership. The practices of Aladura churches often involve cultural elements and rituals that are symbolic rather than physically hazardous. These rituals are part of their broader approach to addressing health and spiritual well-being, which often include the use of streams and mountains for prayer and reflection. The focus is on holistic health, encompassing physical, spiritual, and psychological aspects.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Ethical precepts within Aladura Christianity are deeply intertwined with its cultural and religious practices, reflecting a blend of Christian beliefs and traditional Yoruba values. While specific ethical guidelines vary among different Aladura congregations, the core principles often revolve around living a life of holiness, integrity, and communal harmony, guided by continuous prayer and faith in divine intervention.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Membership in Aladura churches does not require marginalisation by out-group members. Instead, these churches are characterised by their inclusivity and active laity involvement. They reflect the indigenisation of Christianity through the use of African symbols, traditional healing modalities, and worship styles, offering solutions to world problems.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, while not all rituals are mandatory for membership, participation in certain practices, such as prayer and healing rituals, is common among members. These rituals vary in scale from communal worship to more private or household-based activities. The emphasis on prayer and healing within Aladura churches suggests that such practices are integral to the spiritual life of the community.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 3

Notes: The average interval between ritual performances is not explicitly documented and likely varies based on individual church practices and the personal devotion of members. However, the 3 hours of 6, 9, 12, and 3 are very important to them.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Members of Aladura churches often participate in personal and communal prayers, healing services, and the use of holy water, reflecting the indigenisation of Christianity through African symbols and worship styles. While large-scale rituals are not a central requirement, the movement does involve various forms of worship and spiritual practices that align with their beliefs and cultural heritage. Participation in these practices varies among individuals and congregations.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 300000

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 3

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: The Aladura churches are known for their independent and varied practices, which do not often align with traditional Christian orthodoxy, focusing instead on a spiritual experience that resonates with their cultural context.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Notes: While orthopraxy, or correct practice, is important in many religious traditions, Aladura Christianity places a stronger emphasis on individual prayer and divine intervention rather than formalised ritual checks.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Synchronic practices, such as collective prayer and healing services, are common, fostering a sense of unity and shared spiritual experience among members.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: Aladura Christianity does not permit the use of intoxicants.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Aladura Christianity often incorporates cultural values and practices into their worship, which can serve as extra-ritual in-group markers. These may include specific forms of dress, language use, and communal activities that reflect their unique spiritual identity. Such practices help to create a sense of community and belonging among members, distinguishing them from other Christian groups.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: Male children are circumcised among the various Aladura groups in Nigeria.

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, distinctive in-group markers are indeed present, particularly in the form of dress. Members often wear white garments during rituals and services, which serve as a visual expression of their faith and community identity. This practice reflects the movement's emphasis on prayer and spiritual purity, aligning with the meaning of 'Aladura' in Yoruba, which translates to 'owners of prayer' or 'praying people'. The white attire is not just a ritualistic element but also a symbol of their commitment to a life of holiness and spiritual discipline. However, it is not all denominations that partake in this.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, particularly within the Celestial Church of Christ, members often display distinctive extra-ritual in-group markers that signify their identity and beliefs. These can include specific garments and ornaments that are imbued with religious significance. For instance, members are known to abstain from wearing black or red materials except for professional reasons, and certain items like the Sutana, a white garment, and earrings are commonly worn during worship and significant religious ceremonies. Such practices and symbols serve to create a sense of community and continuity among the followers, reflecting their unique spiritual heritage and commitment to their faith's tenets. However, not all the Aladura churches are accustomed to this.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: In Aladura Christianity, a movement predominant in Nigeria, the concept of kinship extends beyond biological ties and incorporates elements of fictive kinship. This is evident in the communal and inclusive nature of the Aladura churches, which often adopt cultural values such as communalism, akin to the 'akodi' system. This system emphasises community support and belonging, reflecting a broader spiritual kinship that resonates with the African understanding of extended family networks. Such practices demonstrate the Aladura churches' adaptation of Christian beliefs to local cultural contexts, fostering a sense of spiritual unity and collective identity among members.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Aladura Christianity is very unlike other forms of Christianity since it has different religious sects that have their own leaders and authorities. This religious group is generally composed of an extensive territory, an enterprise, or a group of sects under different authorities.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not provide any institutionalised famine relief. The group does not provide an organised effort to reduce starvation in its region any time there is famine.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are famine reliefs available to the adherents of this religious group through an institution other than the religious group, especially through the government, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and so on.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Though it is not every time, this religious group usually provides poverty relief to cushion the effect of poverty among its adherents. Depending on how large and rich the particular branch of the group may be, there is the provision of poverty relief, even if it is not institutionalised.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are poverty reliefs available to the adherents of this religious group through institutions other than the religious group, especially the government, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), families, and so on.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group provides care for the elderly and infirm, though this is not usually on a large scale and institutionalised, and the religious group in question is actively involved in it.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There is institutionalised care for the elderly and infirm members of this religious group through an institution other than the religious group. These include the government, nongovernmental organisations (NGOs), and so on.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: This is one aspect that this religious group is very conversant with. From the elementary to the higher institutions, the Aladura movement is very active. They have schools across the country and are very passionate about educational development in the country. There is virtually no particular area in which this movement is not found to be educating people. They have schools for music, theology, entrepreneurship and so on. The Christ Apostolic Church have CAC Theological Seminary, Joseph Ayo Babalola University (JABU) and so many other secondary and primary schools. The Church of the Lord (Aladura) also have schools like the Aladura Comprehensive High School, Aladura Theology Institute and so on. The Cherubim and Seraphim with different factions also have their schools with a university (Moses Orimolade University) that is about to take off. The Celestial Church of Christ has the Celestial Church of Christ High School, Oke Ado Ibadan, Celestial Church of Christ Theological Seminary and so on.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Formal education is not restricted to religious professionals. Since the Aladura movement is a movement of people from different walks of life, there is nothing like formal education being separated for religious professionals only but to all and sundry.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: All religious education is open to both males and females.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not provide public food storage. Even if they have the ability to do this, it will be done for their adherents and not for the public per se.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Public food storage is provided to the adherents of this religious group by the government and nongovernmental organisations (NGOs) other than the religious group.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: This religious group does not provide water management (irrigation, flood control, and so on).

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management is provided to the adherents of this religious group by the government. Just like every other citizen of the country, the adherents of this religious group enjoy the provision of water management (irrigation, flood control, and so on) by the government of the country and other nongovernmental organisations in the country.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not provide transportation infrastructure. Just like every other citizen of the country, the adherents of this religious group enjoy the provision of transportation infrastructure by the government of the country.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Transportation infrastructure is provided to the adherents of this religious group by the government.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: This religious group levies tithes. They accept tithes from their adherents. The payment of tithes is a very important principle that this religious group permits. In fact, some of the churches, like the C&S, even use cards to record tithe payments.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: When it comes to the issue of taxes, the government of the country levies taxes on the adherents of this religious group. This is the function of the government to do.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not provide an institutionalised police force. The question of an institutionalised police force is among the 68 items in the exclusive legislative list in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended), on which only the Federal Government of Nigeria can legislate. No other organisation like this religious group can do this. They know if they do, they are calling for war upon themselves.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents of this religious group interact with an institutionalised police force provided by the government of the Federal Government of Nigeria and any other country of residence. This is the only institutionalised police force permitted by the constitution of the country or any other country of residence where they have their abodes.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Institutionalised judges are provided by the government of any country. This religious group does not provide institutionalised judges. They do not have the power, jurisdiction, or authority to

provide institutionalised judges for their adherents.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents of this religious group interact with an institutionalised judicial system provided by the government of the Federal Government of Nigeria. Whenever there is a writ of summons, they have no choice other than to appear before the court if they wish to defend themselves against the plaintiff's claim, and vice-versa.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not have the power to enforce institutionalised punishment. They cannot make use of sanctions, fines, and incarceration to maintain conformity. This act is meant for the institutionalised police force to do.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Institutionalised punishments like execution depend on the type of offence the offender committed. If the offender kills and the court of law finds him/her guilty and sentences such a person to death, this will be carried out by the law enforcement agencies in charge.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: Institutionalised punishment for exile is not a common practice in the country.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Notes: Institutionalised punishments do not often involve any punishment in which physical force is used and is intended to cause some degree of pain or discomfort.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Ostracism like sending a convicted criminal to prison is a form of punishment that involves isolation from society. This isolation can have a negative impact on the individual's

reintegration into society, as they may face stigma and discrimination upon their release.

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Institutionalised punishments can include the seizure of property. Many convicted criminals have had their properties seized.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: This is an exclusive function of the government. The religious group does not have a formal legal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is an exclusive function of the government. The religious group must abide by and be subjected to the formal legal code as provided by the government.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Institutionalised military is a thing on the exclusive list of the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. If any group whatsoever has any institutionalised military whatsoever, it will amount to having a government under a government. Thus, this religious group, being law-abiding citizens of the country, does not possess an institutionalised military. They believe this is the exclusive function that must be performed by the government alone.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents participate fully in the institutionalised military provided by the government. There are many adherents of the group who are either active or retired military personnel in the Nigerian military. The group does not restrict its members from joining the institutionalised military. In fact, the group sees joining the military as a prestige and honour to the fatherland.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are protected by or even subjected to an institutionalised military provided by an institution other than the religious group in question. One thing about this fact is that they are citizens of the country, which gives them the right to be protected by or subject to an

institutionalised military provided by the government.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: This religious group does not possess its own distinct written language. Despite being diverse (having four distinct groups), it does not have any distinct written language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: A non-religion-specific written language is available to the group's adherents through different institutions of the State.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents of this religious group make use of a non-religion-specific written language through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not have a formal calendar. They make use of the Gregorian calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: A formal calendar is provided for the group's adherents by State institutions. The adherents of this group make use of the Gregorian calendar as being used in some other parts of the world, especially by the Christians.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Since the group is a very large one with subsets all over the country and even beyond, they are involved in agricultural practices mostly in small scale/subsistent farming.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Patoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Since this group interacts with people of other sects and denominations, the adherents ultimately have food provided to them by institutions other than the religious group.

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